

Evaluating the Role and Impact of Digital Mental Health Interventions in Improving Access to Mental Health Services in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Mixed Methods Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

Background: An increasing body of evidence has demonstrated the urgent need to enhance access to mental health services in sub-Saharan Africa through modern, sustainable, and innovative approaches. Despite the growing burden of mental disorders in this region, mental health services continue to be unable to meet this increased demand due to limited resources and prevalent circumstances in this region.

Aims: This research project seeks to reveal and analyse the role and impact of digital mental health interventions in improving access to mental health services in sub-Saharan Africa and evaluate strategies to reduce mental healthcare access gaps in this region with these interventions.

Methodology: This was a mixed-methods systematic review that comprised a methodological exploration across 6 electronic databases between 1st January 2013 and 30th of June 2024 using key search terms and expert evaluation. The quality appraisal of included studies was carried out using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool version 2018. A convergent integrated approach was used to combine data from different study types into primary themes and sub-themes that strongly correlated with the aims and objectives of this study and ultimately resolve the overarching research question.

Result: A total of 838 studies were identified, and 20 studies were included after applying the eligibility criteria to the search results. 4 primary themes and 14 sub-themes were synthesised from the included studies. The primary themes included the expansion of the mental health services pathway, addressing obstacles with traditional mental health services, barriers and facilitators to the utilisation of digital mental health interventions in sub-Saharan Africa.

Conclusion: This study emphasises the pressing need for countries in sub-Saharan Africa to effectively implement digital mental health interventions in large-scale initiatives across mental health services by applying evidence-based recommendations and strategies to address obstacles that impede the optimal benefits of these interventions to significantly bridge the mental healthcare access gap in this region.

LIST OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGMENT	ii
ABSTRACT	iii
LIST OF FIGURES	vi
LIST OF TABLES.....	vi
ABBREVIATIONS	vii
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION.....	1
CHAPTER 2: BACKGROUND	4
2.1 Overview of Mental Health and Mental Disorders	4
2.2 A Synopsis of the Global Mental Health Situation	4
2.3 Outline of the WHO's Initiatives to Incorporate DMHI	6
2.4 The Concept of DMHI	6
2.5 An Overview of the Current State of Mental Health Services in SSA	7
2.6 Research Question.....	8
2.7 Research Aims	9
2.8 Research Objectives	9
2.9 The Levesque et al.'s Patient-centred Access to Healthcare Framework.....	9
CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY	12
3.1 Study Design	12
3.2 Search Technique and Strategy	12
3.3 Eligibility Criteria	14
3.4 Quality Appraisal	16
CHAPTER 4: RESULTS	17
4.1 Included Studies	17
4.2 Quality of Included Studies	18
4.3 Thematic Analysis of Included Studies	18
4.4 Primary Theme 1: Expanding Various Aspects of the Mental Health Services Pathway	20
4.5 Primary Theme 2: Addressing Obstacles with Traditional Mental Health Services	22
4.6 Primary Theme 3: Barriers to the Utilisation of DMHI in SSA.....	22
4.7 Primary Theme 4: Facilitators to the Utilisation of DMHI in SSA	24
4.8 Mapping the Included Studies Using the Healthcare Access Framework.....	25
CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION.....	27
5.1 Overview of Findings	27
5.2 Interpretation of Findings	27

5.3 Examining the Findings from the Healthcare Access Framework	34
5.4 Recommendations for the Optimal Implementation of DMHI in SSA.....	35
5.5 Research Implications	39
CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION	41
6.1 Summarising Synopsis	41
6.2 Examination of the Study's Strengths and Limitations.....	41
REFERENCES	43
APPENDICES.....	63
APPENDIX 1: SEARCH STRATEGY	63
APPENDIX 2: THE MIXED METHODS APPRAISAL TOOL (MMAT), VERSION 2018.....	65
APPENDIX 3: THE MIXED METHODS APPRAISAL RESULTS.....	66
APPENDIX 4: TABLE OF EVIDENCE	67
APPENDIX 5: EXISTING DMHI IDENTIFIED FROM THIS STUDY AND UTILISATION IN MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES ACROSS SSA.....	71

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1: The average number of mental health professionals in relation to the population categorised by the income levels of countries

Figure 2.2: SSA Coverage on the African continent, as indicated by the coloured zone

Figure 2.3: The Healthcare access framework depicting the dimensions of access

Figure 4.1: PRISMA flow chart showing the selection protocol for included studies

Figure 4.2: Graphical representation of the thematic analysis showing the number of included studies that report on each primary theme and sub-theme.

Figure 4.3: Mapping of the included studies using the healthcare access framework

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1: Glossary of key terms and alternate key search terms.

Table 3.2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 4.1: Thematic analysis of included studies

ABBREVIATIONS

ALWH	Adolescents living with HIV
BCI	Brain-computer interface
CBT	Cognitive behavioural therapy
CESD-R	Centre for Epidemiology Studies Depression Scale-Revised
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease
CSC	Collaborative stepped care
DMHI	Digital mental health interventions
EU	European Union
FGDs	Focused group discussions
GCBT	Group cognitive behavioural therapy
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIAI	Guided internet-assisted intervention
HICs	High-income countries
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
ICBT	Internet-based cognitive behavioural therapy
JBI MMSR	Joanna Briggs Institute Updated Methodology for Mixed Methods Systematic Reviews
LMICs	Low- and middle-income countries
MI	Motor imagery
MMAT	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool
MOST	Moderated Online Social Therapy
mCSC	Mobile telephone supported collaborative stepped care
mhGAP-IG	Mental Health Gap Action Programme-Intervention Guide
NF	Neurofeedback
oCSC	Ordinary collaborative stepped care

PICO	Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta Analyses
PST	Problem-solving therapy
PTSD	Post-traumatic stress disorders
RCTs	Randomised controlled trials
SMS	Short message service
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
UN	United Nations
WHO	World Health Organization

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

There is a growing recognition that mental disorders are significant contributors to the overall burden of disease (1). Mental disorders not only cause significant impairment but also increase the likelihood of life-threatening consequences such as suicide and overall morbidity (1). In 2019, there were 970 million people living with a mental disorder, and that number has increased markedly since then (1-2). Unfortunately, access to quality mental health services remains inadequate and inequitable globally (2-3). Furthermore, the various advancements in mental healthcare are further hampered by obstacles to implementation (3). Enhanced access to mental health services for individuals with mental disorders is critically needed, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where there is a high prevalence of challenging socioeconomic and environmental circumstances (4-5).

The prevalent circumstances in many parts of sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), such as poverty and conflicts, increase the risk of mental disorders for residents in this region (6-12). In addition, mental health services in SSA continue to struggle to meet the rapid rise in the mental health needs of its population as availability and quality of services are impeded by limited investment, high treatment costs, stigma, an insufficient number of mental health professionals and infrastructures, and a lack of commitment from policymakers (13-17). Projections indicate an almost 100% increase in the level of disability caused by mental disorders in SSA over the next four decades (18). Digital mental health interventions (DMHI) can provide an innovative and evidence-based approach to enhancing the accessibility of mental health services in SSA, either by complementing existing services or by offering new services to individuals with limited access to traditional mental healthcare (19-20).

The importance of DMHI was further enhanced during the recent coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, which saw an escalation in mental disorders and severe disruption in mental health services (19-23). In addition, the growing digital transformation occurring in SSA, where there has been a recent surge in the number of internet and broadband users, makes it

particularly significant to comprehensively investigate the role that DMHI have in reducing the substantial mental healthcare access gap in this region (24-25). Consequently, the main objective of this review was to thoroughly examine and evaluate the role and impact of DMHI to improve access to mental health services in SSA. Due to my passionate interest in technological advancements for improving mental health and having personally witnessed the significant mental healthcare access barriers in various SSA countries, I decided to carry out this research.

DMHI has shown immense effectiveness and potential to increase access to mental health services. For instance, the United Kingdom and Ireland have already integrated digital cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) services as part of routine care since 2008 and 2022, respectively, which are used either as an independent intervention or in combination with traditional in-person care to provide effective treatment options for adults with depression and anxiety (26). The Moderated Online Social Therapy (MOST) platform, developed in Australia, which combines guided, interactive content with a social network of peers and virtual clinicians, has expanded mental health services for young people in Australia (27). In addition, the use of the MOST platform has demonstrated remarkable improvements in symptoms of depression, anxiety, and psychological distress among Australian youth users (27). Despite the proven impact of DMHI to improve access to mental health services, it is imperative to note that comprehensive, high-quality research on the practical utilisation and implementations of DMHI is relatively new and scarce, particularly in SSA, which poses unique challenges for patients, practitioners, researchers, and policymakers (28-29). To holistically address the challenges associated with DMHI and maximise their benefits, vital research is necessary to gain more insight on ways DMHI can be optimally implemented to increase adequate utilisation and reduce the mental healthcare access gaps in SSA, which elaborates the urgent need for this research project.

This thesis incorporated a mixed methods systematic review to examine the study objectives, and 20 studies from 7 SSA nations met the inclusion criteria. The structure of the thesis is as follows: This introductory chapter has provided a concise summary of the dissertation project.

Chapter 2 provides an in-depth description of the review's foundational concepts, including the research questions, aims, and objectives. Chapter 3 offers a comprehensive and rigorous exposition of the methodology used in this study. Chapter 4 includes an extensive description of the findings. In Chapter 5, the Discussion chapter, I explore suggestions for improving access to mental health services in SSA using DMHI. Chapter 6 offers a brief conclusion.

CHAPTER 2: BACKGROUND

2.1 Overview of Mental Health and Mental Disorders

Mental health refers to a condition of psychological well-being that allows individuals to efficiently navigate the challenges of life, recognise and utilise their capabilities, perform adequately, and make beneficial contributions to their community (30). A mental disorder can be described as a significant distortion to a person's thinking, emotional regulation, or actions that is clinically relevant (31-32).

2.2 A Synopsis of the Global Mental Health Situation

Substantial disparities exist between nations in the quality and availability of mental healthcare. For example, the rates of minimally suitable mental health services in LMICs are 3.7% for individuals with major depression, in contrast to 20.0% in high-income countries (HICs) (5). In recent years, the importance of mental health has increased on a global scale. The United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goal 3.4 and World Health Organization (WHO) Comprehensive Mental Health Action Plan 2013-2030 aim to prevent mental disorders and ensure that people affected by mental disorders have prompt access to high-quality, culturally appropriate health services to foster recovery and achieve the maximum possible level of health (33-34).

Despite some progress, the global burden of mental disorders has not been adequately tackled, leading to significant discrepancies between the necessity for mental health services and their accessibility (34-35). Additionally, the global per capita expenditure on mental health for most LMICs, particularly those in SSA, is significantly less than the suggested \$2 per person (36-37). The notable differences in mental health investments between different income levels in nations also reflect in the number of mental health workers, with LMICs having a far lower proportion of mental health professionals to their population when compared to HICs, as shown in **Figure 2.1**

below, and these discrepancies are significant factors impacting mental health service quality and access (38).

Figure 2.1: The average number of mental health professionals in relation to the population categorised by the income levels of countries (38).

Clearly, it is imperative to allocate more resources towards mental healthcare and provide supplementary services. However, simply increasing funds alone might not resolve the obstacles associated with the availability and quality of mental healthcare. Therefore, progressive solutions must be adopted to tackle the growing burden of mental disorders (3, 39-40).

2.3 Outline of the WHO's Initiatives to Incorporate DMHI

Although there is no specific standalone framework or guideline for DMHI, a broader initiative called the Global Strategy on Digital Health 2020-2025 was created by the WHO in 2021 to provide robust and comprehensive guidance for optimal use and implementation of digital technology in health services to facilitate the advancement of physical and mental health (41).

The key vision of the Global Strategy on Digital Health 2020-2025 is to expedite the adoption and implementation of digital health solutions to encourage equitable and universal access to quality health services. However, a lack of widespread connection access, inadequate infrastructures, and financial limitations in LMICs pose serious obstacles to this vision. (36-38).

2.4 The Concept of DMHI

DMHI encompasses mental health interventions that are offered using any form of digital technology, including mobile applications, internet, artificial intelligence, websites, text messages, virtual reality, wearable devices, and video games (42). These interventions can be used for screening, prevention, education, assessment, management and treatment to enhance the mental health of individuals and can offer standalone or complement existing mental health services (42-43).

Evidence shows that DMHI can be effective in preventing, treating, and managing various mental disorders, including in LMICs (20, 44-46). An example is the Step-by-Step programme, a DMHI developed by the WHO in collaboration with the Ministry of Public Health Lebanon and other partners that provides psychoeducation and behavioural action training that has successfully decreased the levels of depression among Syrian refugees in Lebanon (47). The implementation of the TreadWill app, which provides CBT for depression and anxiety, and the POD Adventures app, which uses gamification to teach students problem-solving ideas for depression and anxiety, has enhanced mental health services in India (48-49).

2.5 An Overview of the Current State of Mental Health Services in SSA

SSA is located south of the Sahara Desert as shown in **Figure 2.2** below. It encompasses 48 countries and a population of 1.21 billion people as of 2022 (7,50). In 2023, there were over 462 million individuals residing in extreme poverty in SSA, a well-established determinant of mental disorders such as depression, anxiety, and schizophrenia (6-9). In addition, by the end of 2023, about 22 out of the 48 countries were characterised as fragile or conflict-affected, while 26 out of the 48 countries are low-income countries, key factors that have adverse effects on the mental health of the populace and access to mental services in those nations (10-12).

Figure 2.2: SSA Coverage on the African continent, as indicated by the coloured zone (51).

Although there has been a huge improvement in health coverage for many nations in SSA, providing sufficient and quality mental health services continues to prove to be a very difficult task (52). Enhancing mental health service coverage relies on increasing investment, ease of access, availability, and proficiency of healthcare professionals to provide patient-focused and comprehensive care (53). Many countries in SSA have a psychiatrist-to-population ratio of only one per million, and the limited number of these practitioners are predominantly in urban areas (15,54). Additionally, there has been an exponential increase in the emigration of health professionals from SSA to HICs in the last two decades, mainly to improve the quality of their lives, which has further decimated the mental health workforce in this region (55-57).

Optimal mental health service utilisation is further impeded by the cultural perspectives, which generally attribute supernatural origins to mental disorders and are accompanied by a widespread stigma (58-60). Research has demonstrated that a lack of understanding about the causes, characteristics, and unfavourable perception of the community towards individuals with mental disorders act as significant obstacles to seeking mental health services in formal settings in SSA (58, 61). Due to the scarcity of professional mental health services and prevalent cultural views, many individuals seek help from spiritual and traditional medicine practitioners, who sometimes engage in abusive behaviours such as assault and food deprivation, which worsen the mental health of patients (36,54,62). Furthermore, most nations in the SSA lack robust mental health legislation, regulations, and policies that adequately safeguard individuals with mental disorders and promote a culturally appropriate atmosphere for mental healthcare (16, 63-64).

2.6 Research Question

What impact does DMHI have on access to mental health services for residents in SSA, considering the role of DMHI in every aspect of mental health services, the huge mental healthcare access gap, and prevalent circumstances in this region?

2.7 Research Aims

This research aims to critically analyse the role and impact of DMHI in improving access to mental health services in SSA and evaluate possible paths to decrease access gaps to mental healthcare through the optimal utilisation and integration of DMHI in mental health services.

2.8 Research Objectives

This research encompassed the following objectives:

Primary Objective

1. To unveil and critically analyse the role and impact of DMHI on access to mental health services in SSA.

Secondary Objectives

2. To identify barriers and facilitators to the utilisation of DMHI in SSA.
3. To provide recommendations for the optimal implementation of DMHI in mental health services to alleviate the mental healthcare access gaps in SSA.

2.9 The Levesque et al.'s Patient-centred Access to Healthcare Framework

Access remains a highly complex and multifaceted concept to universally define and conceptualise. Multiple healthcare access frameworks exist, each possessing distinct advantages and drawbacks. The Levesque et al.'s patient-centred access to healthcare framework, referred to as the healthcare access framework henceforth, was developed from a comprehensive analysis of the corpus of research on accessibility to healthcare (65). This framework defines access as the capacity to identify, undertake, obtain, or utilise healthcare services and ensure that the medical needs for seeking them are fulfilled (65). I utilised the healthcare access framework because it provides a detailed, modern description for understanding healthcare access and considers both the supply and demand dimensions of access, which are highlighted in **Figure 2.3** below (65-66).

Figure 2.3: The Healthcare access framework depicting the dimensions of access (65).

“**Approachability**” includes an individual's capacity to utilise and find available information and resources related to their health needs (65). “**Ability to perceive**” are factors that enable patients to recognise their need for care (65). “**Acceptability**” pertains to the social and cultural criteria to evaluate whether the provided service is deemed acceptable by the patient (65). “**Ability to seek**” is closely tied to the capacity to make informed choices about seeking health services (65). “**Availability and accommodation**” embody the concept that health services, comprising both the amenities for services and the expertise of healthcare practitioners, can be obtained promptly and conveniently (65). “**Ability to reach**” is influenced by factors such as personal mobility and awareness about health services (65).

“Affordability” pertains to the monetary and temporal obligations necessary to obtain a service (65). **“Ability to pay”** refers to the capability to cover the costs of healthcare services without significant depletion of resources for essential needs (65). **“Appropriateness”** refers to the degree of congruence between the specific needs and preferences of the patient and the services that are being offered (65). **“Ability to engage”** in healthcare are factors that enable individuals to connect with service providers (65).

By applying this framework, the critical evaluation process of the crucial variables that influence all facets of access to mental health services was simplified (66). Furthermore, the framework provided a concise way to analyse multiple studies that used different methodologies and synthesise the data and reflections, which removed the tendency to suppress instinctive discovery and ensured an extensive and analytical examination approach of the relevant data (65,67).

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design

This study used a mixed methods systematic review technique in accordance with the Joanna Briggs Institute Updated Methodology for Mixed Methods Systematic Reviews (JBI MMSR) (68). Mixed methods systematic reviews offer a more comprehensive foundation for complex concepts such as access compared to single method reviews, optimising their value for both practical application and policy implementations (68). A systematic review was suitable for identifying a broad spectrum of information on this topic and allowed for the discovery and assessment of appropriate studies, which minimised bias and made the obtained findings reputable for deducing conclusive outcomes (69,70-71). In addition, employing a mixed methods systematic review approach using the JBI MMSR guidelines enabled the synthesis of different types of data through a convergent integrated data approach process that involves the transformation of data in a way that enables an appropriate mix of both quantitative and qualitative data, which ultimately enabled deeper contextual analysis of access in relation to DMHI and mental health services (68).

3.2 Search Technique and Strategy

The electronic databases PsycINFO, Global Health, Medline, and Cochrane were extensively investigated to gather a substantial amount of peer-reviewed scientific literature for this review. Additional searches on the WHO publication library and UN iLibrary were conducted to possibly obtain reliable, relevant data that may not have been peer-reviewed.

I employed the Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome (PICO) protocol to highlight crucial ideas and establish the extent of the study question and aims (72). A blend of search terms derived from previous systematic reviews, research questions, aims, and objectives were

utilised in collaboration with the expertise of the librarians at City St. George's University of London to develop the search strategy. The asterisk (*) was employed to act as a wildcard operator to account for variations in spellings and verb tenses in different scientific literature databases. The key terms and alternate terms used to develop the search strategy are shown in **Tables 3.1** below, and the entire scope of the search strategy for the different databases is in **Appendix 1**.

Key Terms	Description of Key Terms	Alternate Key Search Terms
DMHI	DMHI include any mental health intervention that uses any form of digital technology such as mobile applications or technology, internet websites, virtual reality, text messages, wearable devices, and video games used for providing mental health services.	(technolog* or digital or online or internet or mobile or electronic* or social media or smartphone* or web or app* or "VR" or "AR" or virtual reality or augmented reality or wearable or computer* or message* or personal digital assistant* or PDAS* or laptop* or e-reader* or Enterprise digital assistant* or EDA)
Intervention	Any form of assessment, screening, diagnosis, management, prevention, treatment.	(intervention* or treat* or therap* or screen* or prevent* or manag* or diagnos* or counsel*)
Mental Health Services	Every form of mental health services offered by both traditional and digital methods.	(CBT or cognitive behavioural therapy or eye movement desensitization reprocessing or EMDR or relationship-based interventions or RBIs or systemic interventions or psychoeducation or psychotherapy or Intensive service models or activity-based therapies)
Mental Disorders	A significant distortion to a person's thinking, emotional regulation, or actions that is recognised as being clinically relevant.	(psych* or anxiety or depress* or Schizophreni* or PTSD or trauma* or panic or bipolar)
SSA	Comprises of the 48 countries in SSA (50).	Names of all countries as seen in Appendix 1

Table 3.1: Glossary of key terms and alternate key search terms.

3.3 Eligibility Criteria

A key fundamental focus of the eligibility criteria was to include primary qualitative, mixed methods, and quantitative studies. The concept of DMHI utilisation in mental health services in SSA is relatively new, and access is a very complex concept to critically analyse; hence, different study designs were essential to give in-depth insights to the research question. Various methodologies offer distinct perspectives: quantitative studies such as randomised controlled trials (RCTs) provide unbiased evidence on the effectiveness of interventions; non-randomised studies offer proof of effects of interventions that may not be possible with randomisations; and qualitative research explores the processes and contextual factors involved in access (73-75). Mixed methods studies are useful to identify and evaluate the practical and experimental use of interventions (76).

This review comprehensively analysed the relevant studies from SSA where existing DMHI were utilised in mental health services for anxiety disorders, depressive disorders, bipolar disorders, post-traumatic stress disorders (PTSD), and schizophrenia spectrum disorders. Studies that involved the utilisation of existing DMHI in SSA for overall mental health states were included due to the complex and subjective nature of mental health and the overlapping nature of symptoms between different mental disorders (77). The focus mental disorders of this study are among the most common mental disorders globally and in SSA (1,78). Research has also shown that there is a high prevalence of these specific mental disorders in people affected by conflict and humanitarian situations, which is prominent in many nations in SSA and likely worsened by the severe mental healthcare access barriers in this region. (12-13).

To ensure the appropriate use of the concepts of the JBI MMSR guidelines, quantitative research and mixed methods studies were only included if they investigated any access concepts defined in the healthcare access framework (65, 68). Moreover, in evaluating concepts such as access, the proven effectiveness of DMHI alone may not be sufficient to justify

improving access; therefore, far-reaching broader insights and concepts must be considered, hence the careful methodological approach for the eligibility criteria of studies for this review (68, 77). Studies that met the specific criteria for inclusion and exclusion detailed in **Table 3.2** below were selected for analysis.

Eligibility Criteria	Rationale	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Publication Date	I utilised this time frame to keep up with the development in DMHI in line with the WHO Comprehensive Mental Health Action Plan 2013-2030 (34).	Published from 01/01/2013-30/06/2024	Published before 2013
Methodology of Publication Types	Primary research studies of all study types including qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods studies.	Primary studies that align with the question, objectives and aim of this study	Systematic reviews to avoid duplication of studies. Case reports, case studies were also be excluded
Language	There were no language restrictions to include all the possible data.	Studies published in all languages	None
Mental Disorders/Mental Health	The review focused on 5 mental disorders: anxiety disorders, depressive disorders, bipolar disorder, PTSD, schizophrenia spectrum disorders and overall mental health state.	Studies reporting on the 5 focus mental disorders and overall mental health state	Studies that reported on use of DMHI use in other mental disorders and/either no overall mental health state
Age of Participants	No age restrictions	All ages	None
Geographical Location	The research question and objectives focus on SSA	Within SSA	Outside SSA
Intervention Settings	Capturing the places DMHI are utilised for mental health services in SSA	Every setting was considered	None
Location of Research Participants	Ensure harmonious alignment within regional settings	Residents in SSA	Residents outside SSA
Mental Health Services	All forms of mental health services that involve the 'utilisation' of existing DMHI was investigated in every aspect of service provision, including screening, assessment, diagnosis, prevention, education, treatment, improvement, and management.	Mental health services with existing DMHI	Mental health services without existing DMHI

Table 3.2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

3.4 Quality Appraisal

All the included studies were assessed using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) version 2018 shown in **Appendix 2** (79). The MMAT was designed to serve as a checklist for concurrently evaluating and/or describing articles that are included in mixed methods systematic reviews. It is also highly efficient as it enables the simultaneous evaluation of the most prevalent forms of empirical research using a single instrument, evaluating the quality of research that employs mixed methods (assessing the qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods components) (79). In addition, the content of this tool has been extensively verified and approved using input from experts and workshops with extensive reliability testing (79). While the MMAT does not focus extensively on metrics, satisfactory quality ratings are usually 60% of criteria met and above.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

4.1 Included Studies

The selection of studies for this review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines illustrated in **Figure 4.1** below (80). Included studies were selected through rigorous utilisation of the eligibility criteria depicted in **Table 3.2** of the previous chapter on the search results from the 6 electronic databases. An overall of 74 studies underwent full screening, and 20 studies from 7 countries in SSA met the specified inclusion requirements (81-100). 7 from South Africa, 5 from Kenya, 3 from Nigeria, 2 from Zambia, and 1 each from Rwanda, Ghana, and Zimbabwe. Among the included studies, there were 5 mixed methods, 3 qualitative, and 12 quantitative studies (9 RCTs and 3 non-randomised studies) (81-100).

Figure 4.1: PRISMA flow chart showing the selection protocol for included studies (80).

4.2 Quality of Included Studies

All the included studies obtained satisfactory quality criteria (60% quality criteria met and above), and the appraisal results were used to guide the analysis and interpretation of this review. 12 of the included studies received a quality score of 60%, 5 received an 80% rating, and 3 received a 100% rating. The quality appraisal procedure for the included studies is detailed in **Appendix 3**.

4.3 Thematic Analysis of Included Studies

The included studies were thematically synthesised using the convergent integrated approach detailed in the JBI MMSR to comprehensively examine and identify primary themes and subthemes, as presented in **Table 4.1** and **Figure 4.2** below (68). Additionally, an in-depth tabulation of evidence in **Appendix 4** was produced, which provides a concise overview of all the studies included in the review, offering readers, researchers, and policymakers a succinct summary of the initial analysis. A noteworthy compendium of all the existing DMHI and their utilisation in mental health services identified from this study was also summarised in **Appendix 5**.

Study Reference	Primary Theme 1: Expanding Various Aspects of the Mental Health Services Pathway			Primary Theme 2: Addressing Obstacles with Traditional Mental Health Services in SSA		Primary Theme 3: Barriers to the Utilisation of DMHI in SSA					Theme 4: Facilitators to the Utilisation of DMHI in SSA			
	Sub-Themes	1.1 Scaling up Screening and Assessment Services for Mental Disorders	1.2 Tools to Improve the Symptoms of Mental Disorders	1.3 Enhancing Traditional Mental Health Service Delivery	2.1 Addressing Stigma	2.2 Extended Geographical Reach	3.1 Technological Limitations	3.2 Security Concerns	3.3 Low Digital Literacy	3.4 Inadequate Designs of DMHI	3.5 Financial Limitations	4.1 Ease and Convenience of use	4.2 Accelerated Mental Health Services	4.3 Fully Remote Access to Mental Health Services
(81)	√										√	√		
(82)		√	√	√	√		√				√		√	
(83)		√	√	√					√		√		√	
(84)		√	√	√	√	√					√			√
(85)		√	√	√		√					√		√	√
(86)						√	√	√	√	√				√
(87)	√			√	√						√	√	√	
(88)		√	√	√							√	√		
(89)		√	√	√	√	√					√		√	
(90)		√	√	√		√		√	√					
(91)		√	√	√							√			√
(92)		√	√	√					√					√
(93)		√	√	√										√
(94)		√	√	√										
(95)		√	√	√										
(96)		√												
(97)		√												
(98)		√	√	√										
(99)		√											√	
(100)		√	√	√										
Total	2	17	14	4	5	5	2	2	4	1	9	3	6	5

Table 4.1: Thematic analysis of included studies.

Figure 4.2: Graphical representation of the thematic analysis showing the number of included studies that report on each primary theme and sub-theme.

4.4 Primary Theme 1: Expanding Various Aspects of the Mental Health Services

Pathway

Sub-Theme 1.1: Scaling up Screening and Assessment Services for Mental Disorders

DMHI could be adaptable for screening and assessing mental disorders in a variety of settings. For instance, a study in Kenya showed that using DMHI can increase screening services in remote rural settings with limited mental health professionals and facilities (81). Another study in South Africa demonstrated the use of DMHI as a tool for online mental disorder screening (87).

Sub-Theme 1.2: Tools to Improve the Symptoms of Mental Disorders

Most studies found that using DMHI in mental health services improved symptoms of all five focus mental disorders for this review (82-85,88-100). A study in Rwanda found that DMHI was able to produce clinically meaningful alleviation of symptoms in patients diagnosed with PTSD (97). Another study in Ghana indicated that DMHI played a crucial role in improving the symptoms of patients diagnosed with schizophrenia, bipolar, and depression (91).

While DMHI improved symptoms of mental disorders in most studies, a study in Zambia that investigated the effectiveness of online counselling showed stark contrast, as most service users did not experience any improvement in their symptoms and were not satisfied with the use of online counselling (86).

Sub-Theme 1.3: Enhancing Traditional Mental Health Service Delivery

DMHI showed that they can increase the efficacy of traditional mental health services and provide a platform for traditional mental health service delivery (82-85,88-95,98,100). In Nigeria, adding mobile telephone adherence support to a collaborative stepped care (CSC) increased patient engagement and adherence to depression management methods in primary health settings (88). Similarly, studies in South Africa that reported on the use of internet-based CBT (ICBT) and online group CBT (GCBT) in university students highlighted how DMHI can also be used to enhance the service delivery of existing traditional mental health services such as CBT (82-83).

Broader utilisation of DMHI beyond mental healthcare services was also identified. In Kenya, WhatsApp was used to deliver mental health support for human immunodeficiency virus (HIV)-positive adolescents, and it demonstrated simultaneous improvements in their mental health and adherence to anti-retroviral medications (89). Studies conducted in Kenya and South Africa also used DMHI to provide mental health support in abortion care that improved both mental health and overall health outcomes for service users (92-93).

4.5 Primary Theme 2: Addressing Obstacles with Traditional Mental Health Services

Sub-Theme 2.1: Addressing Stigma

DMHI address stigma mainly through offering greater privacy (82,84,87,89). Gericke et al.'s study (82) found that the anonymous use of ICBT helped university students overcome the stigma associated with traditional in-person campus services. Some students described the university's counselling centre as "very public" and expressed concerns about the stigma of using campus-based services to peers, which contributed to the high adoption and use of ICBT (p. 796). Another study in Kenya showed that DMHI was able to afford service users the privacy to avoid stigma related to mental disorders and HIV diagnosis (89).

Sub-Theme 2.2: Extended Geographical Reach

Studies in Kenya, Zimbabwe, Zambia, and Nigeria showed that DMHI can be used to provide mental health services for people in diverse locations, including those in far rural areas, and ensure that individuals receive services either simultaneously or at different times, which is typically not feasible with traditional mental health services that are often restricted to a particular place or facility (81,84-87). Additionally, when there were enforced restrictions on movement, such as during the COVID-19 pandemic, essential mental health services could still be provided through DMHI (85-86).

4.6 Primary Theme 3: Barriers to the Utilisation of DMHI in SSA

Sub-Theme 3.1: Technological Limitations

Poor connectivity and lack of access to digital devices were the two main technological limitations identified in this review (84-87, 89-90). Poor connectivity was the predominant technological barrier, posing a significant challenge to DMHI utilisation. A study in Zimbabwe revealed that poor connectivity caused numerous complaints from both service users and providers when using a mobile application for problem-solving therapy (PST) (84). Two studies in Zambia found that poor internet connectivity caused severe disruptions in mental health service delivery (85-86).

Limited access to digital devices was also another technological limitation that was discovered. A study in Kenya showed that restricted access to mobile phones disrupted service users' engagement with the service (89). Similarly, in Zambia, irregular availability of communication devices for telephone-delivered sessions resulted in participants missing sessions (85).

Sub-Theme 3.2: Security Concerns

Perceived level of security with using DMHI was observed to play an important role in the level of appeal to service users. (82,86). In a Zambian study, the service providers' access to personal data made many service users highly suspicious of potential scams (86). In another study in South Africa, university students were concerned about the risk of cybersecurity breaches associated with DMHI, as they cited previous breaches in popular digital platforms that exposed service users' details (82).

Sub-Theme 3.3: Low Digital Literacy

Low digital literacy among health professionals hinders the utilisation of DMHI (86,90). Researchers in Zambia found that a considerable proportion of experienced therapists lacked computer proficiency, undermining the use of online counselling, as the study found online counselling to be ineffective in that context (86). In another study in South Africa, mental health nurses struggled to interact properly with the text messaging system, which compromised the process of confirming and rescheduling appointments, which may have skewed the study findings, which indicated that the system was not practical to use in that format (90).

Sub-Theme 3.4: Inadequate Designs of DMHI

The design of DMHI plays a crucial role in determining whether service users and service providers adequately engage and utilise DMHI in mental health services (86). In a South African study, certain participants reported that the absence of clear visual cues hindered their engagement and obstructed the therapeutic process of online GCBT (83). A Zambian study showed that most service users preferred video conference calls over text or voice call formats for online counselling delivery (86).

Sub-Theme 3.5: Financial Limitations

The review found limited information on reports that investigated the financial limitations associated with using DMHI. Only one study, conducted in Zambia, examined the direct impact of financial constraints on DMHI utilisation, and it revealed that both service users and service providers faced significant challenges in purchasing data bundles for internet access due to the high cost of these bundles, despite the necessity of good internet access for accessing and supplying the service (86).

4.7 Primary Theme 4: Facilitators to the Utilisation of DMHI in SSA

Sub-Theme 4.1: Ease and Convenience of Use

A significant number of reports highlighted that the ease and convenience associated with using DMHI drives the demand for their use (81-85,87-89 91). A study in Kenya reported that an online platform for mental health support provided a convenient environment for service users to easily express themselves and share their feelings more openly than in other settings without the concern of incurring negative consequences, which enhanced the use of the DMHI (89). In Ghana, traditional healers found the M-Healer app, which educates them on better practices easy to navigate, and it encouraged the utilisation (91).

Sub-Theme 4.2: Accelerated Mental Health Services

Faster delivery of mental health services was a key factor in the utilisation of DMHI (81,87-88). Studies in Kenya and South Africa showed that the immediate feedback that was received from an online screening tool for depression was well received and added to the appeal of the DMHI to both service users and providers, as it allowed for additional benefits of saving time and avoiding opportunity cost associated with delay in assessing mental health services (81,87).

Sub-Theme 4.3: Fully Remote Access to Mental Health Services

Some DMHI offer fully remote mental health services, which facilitates their use (82-83,84,87,89,99). In Zambia, remote access to mental health services using telephone sessions eliminated logistic obstacles that are associated with travel to a health facility (85). Similarly, Nigerian university students were able to receive a 10-week guided internet-assisted intervention (GIAI) from home to reduce the symptoms of depression, which encouraged the students to use the intervention (99).

Sub-Theme 4.4: Trained Service Providers

The knowledge and expertise of service providers were seen to be crucial to the utilisation of DMHI, particularly for mental health services that require the interaction of service users and providers (84–86, 91–93). In Zambia, service users reiterated that the knowledge and communication skills of their service providers were critical to fostering a feeling of ease, confidence, and involvement that permitted a strong therapeutic connection, which highlighted the key role adequately trained service providers can play in the uptake of DMHI (85).

4.8 Mapping the Included Studies Using the Healthcare Access Framework

Each included study was conceptualised within each of the five dimensions of the healthcare access framework, showing the demand and supply dimensions as detailed in **Appendix 4**. **Figure 4.3** below provides a succinct summary of the results of the mapping of included studies using the healthcare access framework.

Figure 4.3: Mapping of the included studies using the healthcare access framework.

The major focus of the article included in the review fell on the “**Appropriateness/Ability to engage**” dimension. All 20 studies reported on this dimension and emphasised the importance of effectiveness and meeting service users’ mental health needs with the use of DMHI (81-100). The dimension of “**Acceptability/Ability to seek**” was the second most highlighted dimension with 11 studies (82-85, 88-92,96,98). Several studies showed that cultural factors such as stigma attached to mental disorders, influenced DMHI acceptance (82-83,85,89). The dimension of “**Availability and Accommodation/Ability to reach**” emerged as third, with 8 reports investigating this dimension (81-82,84-86,89-90). Important factors such as availability to remote access to mental health care were crucial to drive the reach of DMHI, particularly during challenging circumstances (85). The dimension of “**Approachability/Ability to perceive**” was reported in only 2 studies (82, 86). However, it was apparent that mental health services involving DMHI may be made more approachable through transparency and clear information. Finally, the dimension of “**Affordability/Ability to pay**” was the least mentioned, with only 1 study reporting on the impact of financial limitations on individuals’ ability to invest in mental services, which indicated that service providers and users struggled to afford the service (86).

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

5.1 Overview of Findings

This study seems to be a novel endeavour to perform a systematic evaluation on the role and impact of DMHI on access to mental health services in SSA. This review points to a range of insights that shows that DMHI may have a transformative impact on access to mental health services in SSA. However, preliminary analysis of the findings suggested that a complex interplay of different factors at different levels characterises the role and impact of existing DMHI to bridge the present substantial gap in mental healthcare in SSA.

5.2 Interpretation of Findings

This section provides an extensive analysis of the diverse concepts gathered from the findings, allowing for deeper insights and reflections with adequate considerations of the aims and objectives of this research.

Primary Theme 1: Expanding Various Aspects of the Mental Health Services Pathway

The findings indicate that there are three ways that DMHI can expand aspects of the mental health services pathway. Firstly, by scaling up screening and assessment services for mental disorders, DMHI can bolster early identification of mental disorders, which forms one of the key foundational bases for improving mental health services in limited resource settings such as SSA (5). Interestingly, the data on the use of DMHI for screening and assessment focused exclusively on depressive disorders, which indicates a startling lack of research into the use of DMHI for identification of other mental disorders (81,87). Broader literature indicates that depression is the most studied mental disorder and among the most prevalent and incapacitating in SSA, with many individuals in this region rarely receiving diagnosis or treatment, which may explain the drive to find methods to facilitate earlier diagnosis of this disorder (101-103).

Secondly, DMHI can be used as tools to improve symptoms of mental disorders. In most of the included studies, DMHI had a significant impact on improving symptoms of all five mental disorders focus of this review, which is consistent with wider literature (44-46, 82-85, 88-100). Despite the strong indication that DMHI can improve symptoms of mental disorders, a strong correlation was also discovered between the appropriateness of the DMHI, and the levels of symptom improvement experienced by service users (82-83,86). This correlation was apparent in Zambia, where online counselling was considered not effective, despite proven success outside SSA (86,104). I postulate that this indicates an underutilisation of pre-implementation research for DMHI involving service users and providers in SSA to gain valuable data beforehand on suitable implementation methods that navigate challenges in practical DMHI usage.

Also, DMHI immensely improved traditional mental health service delivery from the findings of this review. (83-85) Surprisingly, none of the included studies reported on the use of DMHI as a preventive measure for mental disorders. I assert that the focus on DMHI for mainly treatment of mental disorders reflects the priority of existing mental health programmes and funding allocations in SSA (6,18). The funding of most mental health services in SSA is usually geared towards treatments of mental disorders, particularly for severe cases, highlighting a historical pattern of most nations in SSA ignoring a prevention-based approach to tackling health challenges (6,18). Additionally, the use of DMHI in abortion care and HIV may indicate potential future ample use of DMHI to improve health in the wider ecosystem of healthcare (89,92-93). I postulate that due to the evident high risk of mental disorders, particularly for individuals with chronic physical illness and vice versa, in addition to the growing burden of non-communicable diseases in SSA, DMHI may have a far-reaching beneficial impact in health services in SSA that improves mental and physical health (105-107).

Primary Theme 2: Addressing Obstacles with Traditional Mental Health Services in SSA

Addressing stigma and extended geographical reach were the two main ways that DMHI can tackle the typical obstacles associated with traditional mental health services. Stigma surrounding mental disorders is deeply rooted in the social and cultural fabric of many parts of SSA, which often discriminates against individuals with mental disorders, thus hindering their ability to seek mental health services (6). DMHI helps in alleviating this significant obstacle to mental health services in ways that traditional mental health services may not offer through greater levels of privacy to tackle the long-standing stigma associated with mental health and mental disorders in SSA (82,108). I argue that while DHMHs offer the advantage of privacy to tackle the stigma-related barriers to mental health services in SSA, the issue of stigma represents an ingrained problem in this region and must be addressed holistically and not masked, as stigma can also prevent the utilisation of DMHI in effective forms such as group therapy or DMHI that are geared towards only enhancing existing traditional mental health services (109).

The ability of DMHI to have a broader geographic reach is of immense importance in SSA, a region characterised by a huge proportion of the population living in rural areas, who often suffer limitations in the quality and availability of mental health services when compared to urban areas (110,111). I argue that while the implementation of DMHI for mental health services could improve access for the population in hard-to-reach locations, significant barriers such as the unequal distribution of basic amenities may likely impact the equitable distribution of the availability and quality of services provided with DMHI across different geographical locations in SSA, which might end up increasing the current inequities in access to mental healthcare across SSA (112).

Primary Theme 3: Barriers to the Utilisation of DMHI in SSA

Technological limitations, security concerns, low digital literacy, inadequate designs of DMHI, and financial limitations were identified as significant barriers that impede the utilisation of DMHI in SSA. The emergence of poor connectivity as the major technological limitation barrier in SSA was not surprising. Connectivity, particularly internet connection, is a major challenge in SSA in terms of reliability and quality, which often depend on geographical location. Internet and mobile connections exhibit greater speed and enhanced stability in most urban regions in SSA compared to rural areas due to the higher presence of network infrastructures and mobile broadband coverage (113-116). Also, the limited availability and ownership of personal digital devices common in SSA poses another technological limitation to utilising DMHI (85, 89). I argue that the issue of connectivity poses a significant obstacle to the equitable and sufficient widespread use of DMHI, given its crucial role in enabling the basic functionality of most DMHI. Furthermore, design, development, and utilisation of DMHI that bypass connectivity issues is extremely difficult, as most DMHI typically require internet or mobile connectivity for functionality (81,82,86).

The issue of security concerns being identified as a barrier to transmit trust in service users to utilise DMHI is consistent with broader literature, as there has been long-standing debate on the safety of DMHI, particularly with an ever-increasing global and regional cybersecurity threat and data breaches (42,82,86,117). I contend that the lack of robust cybersecurity infrastructures in SSA makes easing security concerns extremely challenging, as indicated by the low ranking of most nations in SSA in the most recent global cybersecurity index that assesses the level of dedication of governments towards cybersecurity (118).The poor state of current cybersecurity and data protection protocols in SSA means reassuring service users of their safety concerns with DMHI will likely be met with high pessimism, ultimately negatively impacting the utilisation of DMHI (118).

Low digital literacy was also an important barrier identified in this study. Extensive research in SSA has also found a substantial deficiency in digital literacy among health workers, demonstrating inadequate digital literacy skills, which aligns with the findings from this review (86,119-120). Low digital literacy affects the ability of service providers to deliver high-quality mental health services with DMHI (86, 119–120). Despite the rapid digital transformation in SSA, overall digital literacy is still low compared to other regions of the world, which could also prevent adequate service users' engagement with DMHI (121). I assert that the low digital literacy in the general population of SSA creates enormous doubts about the large-scale implementation and adoption of DMHI, as this might further compromise mental health services if DMHI are not correctly utilised and consequently damage the prospects of implementation and acceptance of DMHI.

Another key barrier to the utilisation of DMHI was the inadequate designs of DMHI. A viable connection exists between the design of DMHI, quality of service provision, service users' engagement, and therapeutic value of the intervention (83,86). Prior investigations have established strong links between the perceived value and engagement of service users with DMHI and the design of DMHI, which underscores the importance of designing DMHI to optimise service user engagement. (122-123). I argue that insufficient considerations of service users' perspectives and the current socioeconomic context of SSA during the development and design phases of many DMHI are likely to have caused inadequate utilisation of DMHI stemming from foundational design challenges of DMHI observed in some reports (82-83,86,90).

Finally, financial limitations were a major but underreported barrier to DMHI utilisation. The importance of financial consideration to DMHI utilisation is immense in SSA, as this region has the largest number of people living in extreme poverty, which is likely to remain in the range of 9 in 10 persons by 2030 (124-125). For instance, internet or mobile connectivity, which is typically needed for DMHI, is unaffordable for most individuals in SSA, in contrast to HICs,

where connectivity is nearly universally accessible and affordable (86,126-127). I assert that although most included studies in this review covered the cost of DMHI and the associated mental health services primarily for research purposes, this may not accurately reflect the actual cost of implementing DMHI in mental health services in SSA, particularly due to the current mental health financing models in most parts of SSA, which often involve a large portion of out-of-pocket payments, potentially making the use of DMHI prohibitively expensive and unsustainable for most individuals in this region (6,23,128).

Primary Theme 4: Facilitators to the Utilisation of DMHI in SSA

Four facilitators to the utilisation of DMHI in SSA were uncovered from this review. First, the ease and convenience associated with using DMHI was an important facilitator to the use of DMHI, as it influenced service users' and providers' engagement and perception of effectiveness (81-82). I argue that these findings align with the consequences of the present challenges in mental healthcare in SSA, clearly demonstrating that individuals in this region urgently require readily available mental health services free from the typical systemic barriers and obstacles that are usually associated with existing traditional mental health services (23). This may further indicate that DMHI with proven effectiveness, but complex modes of use may not be equipped to meet the mental healthcare demands of people in this region.

Second, accelerated mental health services was identified as a critical facilitator for DMHI utilisation. Mental health services are usually slow in SSA due to the severe shortage of various mental health resources, including mental health professionals and facilities (3). This shortage has disrupted the timing and availability of services for residents in SSA, increasing the embrace of accelerated mental health services that some DMHI provide (81,87-88). These findings from this review are consistent with broader research that shows that rapid mental health services offered by DMHI encouraged their use (129-130). I assert that despite the necessary and urgent need to accelerate mental health services, the lack of regulation of DMHI in SSA might worsen the quality of mental health services due to a rapid surge in low-

quality DMHI in the mental health field lacking proper validation since the COVID-19 pandemic (131-132).

Next, the fully remote access to mental health services that some DMHI offer was a valuable facilitator to the utilisation of DMHI in contexts such as SSA, particularly where and when traditional mental health service provision is practically impossible in some cases due to socioeconomic and environmental factors seen in some reports (85, 87). Fully remote services can also provide the added benefit of saving time and avoiding the risk of travelling in conflict zones (133-134). Consequently, large-scale adoption of fully remote mental health services could be beneficial in alleviating the huge burden that mental disorders place on health systems in SSA. However, I argue that optimism for increasing fully remote access to mental health services in SSA with DMHI must be met with strong caution due to the prevalent socioeconomic and technological barriers, which make the feasibility and sustainability of remote mental health services challenging.

Finally, the impact of trained service providers as crucial facilitators to the utilisation of DMHI from this study was captivating, as it showed that the proficiency of service providers in efficiently providing services with DMHI is not necessarily related to their qualifications or level of education, but the training and experience they have with the use of the specific DMHI, which highlights the potential of DMHI to improve task shifting and task sharing as well as the need for comprehensive tailored training with the use of DMHI (81,86). These findings increase the evidence of closing mental health access gaps in resource-limited settings such as SSA with task shifting and task sharing involving lay professionals (6,135-136). DMHI may make these transitions much more seamless, which compliments the growing evidence that backs task shifting and task sharing with extensive research that has been conducted in SSA and beyond (135-136). I further deduce that the presence of adequately trained service providers for DMHI may further enhance research and development by facilitating essential feedback loops from service users to developers and researchers, enabling better integration of DMHI for optimal benefits.

5.3 Examining the Findings from the Healthcare Access Framework

The major focus of articles included in the review fell into the “**Appropriateness/Ability to engage**” dimension. I postulate that this indicates the current critical need to accurately understand the efficacy of DMHI and their influence on the overall availability and quality of mental health services in SSA to gain more evidence for their implementation. This further highlight that the concept of implementing DMHI in mental health services is in the early stages of adoption in most healthcare systems in SSA, hence the need to gain more fundamental knowledge in the areas of effectiveness and service users’ perspectives of DMHI capacities to meet their mental health needs.

The dimension of “**Acceptability/Ability to seek**” was the second most highlighted dimension. The major advantages that DMHI offers, such as greater privacy and the possibility of fully remote services, significantly help navigate the typical barriers associated with traditional mental health services, which is likely the key link to increasing the acceptance of DMHI among residents of SSA. I claim that the historic impact the dominant cultural, societal values, and beliefs in SSA have had on access to traditional mental health services has precipitated the need for researchers, practitioners, and DMHI developers to strongly investigate how these cultural and social factors would also influence acceptance and intention towards DMHI use in mental health services.

Thirdly, the “**Availability and accommodation/Ability to reach**” dimension emerged in several investigations. The results from this dimension are in line with what the larger literature review found, which indicates that social determinants of health are likely to play a big role in how DMHI is distributed and made available across and within SSA countries, especially when it is used on a broader level (137). I contend that without addressing the existing inequities in the social determinants of health, particularly at national and regional levels in SSA, similar inequities would be spilt over in large-scale use of DMHI, which might make the availability and reach of mental health services more challenging.

The dimension of “**Approachability/Ability to perceive**” was reported in very few studies. I assert that initiatives to make DMHI more appealing to service users in SSA have not been well investigated by researchers, practitioners, and relevant stakeholders, which in turn has not enhanced the trust and beliefs of service users to increase their perceived need for DMHI.

Finally, the dimension of “**Affordability/Ability to pay**” being the least mentioned dimension, highlighted the distinct lack of research on the cost of implementing DMHI to service users and healthcare systems. I argue that the limited data on this dimension implies a lack of quality and cost-focused research on DMHI in SSA, signifying the neglect of vital yet necessary access components, which may be a result of the unreadiness of many nations in SSA to widely adopt DMHI into their healthcare systems.

5.4 Recommendations for the Optimal Implementation of DMHI in SSA

5.41: Digital Literacy and DMHI Training Initiatives

Lack of sufficient practical knowledge of service providers on the utilisation of DMHI due to low digital literacy has a significant negative impact on the effectiveness and appropriateness of mental health services that involve the use of DMHI (86,90). Countries in SSA can use comprehensive digital literacy and DMHI training initiatives at every level of their healthcare systems to increase digital literacy, which would make service providers proficient with DMHI and incorporate the skills they need to adequately utilise existing and new DMHI (138).

Regular mandatory training on various DMHI can equip the mental health workforce with the necessary skills and practical knowledge to effectively utilise these interventions, thereby enhancing the quality of mental health services. Implementing these training initiatives would have a cascading effect on improving task shifting and task sharing by allowing appropriate dispersal of duties to lay mental health professionals to increase supply of mental health services and reduce the burden of the mental health work force shortage in SSA (139).

5.42: Careful Considerations in the Design and Development of DMHI

The findings from this review have established the importance of the design of DMHI in improving mental health services (83, 86). It is essential that in the development and design of DMHI for use in SSA, the prevalent technological and socioeconomic circumstances are adequately considered to ensure that DMHI that are used in this region are adaptable, practical, and sustainable to have a beneficial impact on increasing access to quality mental health services (140-141).

For instance, Android smart phones are more common in SSA when compared to iPhones due to their affordability (84,142). The Inuka application utilised in Zimbabwe, which offers PST that has successfully improved symptoms of depression and anxiety, was developed with that concession in mind; the Android version of the application was first designed to increase utilisation due to the dominance of the Android smartphone market in Zimbabwe and SSA (84). Important considerations to the cost of using DMHI or tools to access mental health services involving DMHI must ensure that these costs are affordable to most residents in SSA for equitable access. Therefore, existing and future designs and developments of DMHIs must carefully consider important prevalent circumstances in SSA to maximise their implementation.

5.43: Improving Connectivity

This review revealed that connectivity is a major obstacle to the proper utilisation of DMHI (85-86). With the technological barriers in SSA, DMHI that bypass connectivity and other technological barriers may seem the best option to improve their implementation. However, the practicality of such DMHI is very low, as most forms of digital technological tools require connectivity to be optimally implemented; therefore, it is imperative to improve connectivity in this region, which will simultaneously improve the economies of countries in SSA (140,143). Evidence has shown that improving connectivity can enhance productivity and bolster the economy by facilitating the integration of remote populations into global markets, improving

citizens' access to societal services, boosting educational and employment opportunities, and encouraging innovation (140,143-144). In SSA, Google's internet products and services generated over \$30 billion in revenue between 2021 and 2023, with the potential to reach \$180 billion by 2025 (145). Countries in SSA can improve their economic prospects by investing in better connectivity, which will generate more funds for mental health services and provide an enabling environment for DMHI.

Despite some improvements, SSA remains the region with the highest levels of connectivity gaps, with nearly half of the worldwide population without access to mobile broadband residing in this region (146). Subsidising the cost of internet and mobile connectivity by governments in this region could enable more individuals to have equitable access to DMHI, particularly for those in the rural areas (147). A beneficial example for countries in SSA to improve connectivity would be to emulate the Chinese government's staunch effort to improve internet connectivity and penetration for its huge population by subsidising and providing loans to local-based technological companies, which resulted in cheaper and excellent connectivity across the nation and ultimately huge progress in high-quality connectivity for both urban and rural communities in the last 10 years (147-148).

5.44: Adequate Implementation of Initiatives to Enhance Safety of DMHI

Many countries in the SSA lack adequate legislation to ensure the protection of service users, which makes implementing hardline safety protocols for DMHI challenging. As of January 2024, only 32 of the 48 SSA countries had implemented a data protection law, with one-third of these laws enacted in the previous five years (149-150).

However, the lack of efficient regional collaboration and knowledge sharing among countries in SSA is the biggest obstacle impeding efforts to combat cybercrime and increase the security of digital technological tools and processes (151-153). A comprehensive look at the multiple initiatives model used by the European Union (EU) shows a more efficient method for SSA to follow. The EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) enforced in 2018 is the strictest

security and privacy legislation in the world, designed to force businesses and organisations in the EU to integrate security measures based on the level of risk associated with the data processing operations they carry out, which has resulted in a considerable decrease in data breaches (154-157).

The EU, in response to the increase in cyberattacks since the inception of the Russia-Ukraine war that started in 2022, adopted in January 2024 a single EU-wide cybersecurity certification scheme that guarantees elevated cybersecurity requirements for digital products, services, and procedures (158–159). Additionally, the EU has enacted union-wide legislation measures that ensure a consistent and elevated standard of cybersecurity throughout the union to enhance the trust of users (158). These security initiatives have resulted in a reduction in data breaches since February 2024 and strengthened the future cyber resilience of the EU (158,160). By adopting and implementing a comprehensive single framework for cybersecurity and digital technology across SSA, there will be beneficial coordinated regional efforts against cybercrime and increased safety and trust among service users regarding the use of DMHI.

5.45: Development of a Unified Framework for DMHI

At the time of writing this review, no global framework exists specifically guiding the use of DMHI in mental health services. Leading health organisations such as the WHO, which has led the development of important guidelines such as the Global Strategy on Digital Health 2020-2025 mentioned in Chapter 2, must urgently develop a specific framework and standard guideline that govern the implementation and utilisation of DMHI to ensure standardised mental health service quality (41).

Additionally, a framework for DMHI must be developed with adequate consideration of the healthcare systems and socioeconomic situations of different regions. For instance, the WHO Mental Health Gap Action Programme-Intervention Guide (mhGAP-IG), which comprises therapies aimed at both preventing and managing prevalent mental disorders in non-specialist health settings, has had a substantial influence on the education and promotion of mental

health on a global scale, including in SSA (161-162). The mhGAP-IG has strengthened the confidence of lay mental health professionals in managing mental disorders and created a platform where practitioners from various international contexts can benefit from each other's experiences and modify intervention approaches to fit their own context (162). Therefore, the development of an evidence-based, unified framework for DMHI implementation for different mental disorders would be useful in enhancing access to quality mental health services in SSA.

5.46: Promote Multi-Sectoral Partnership and Collaboration

Multi-sectoral partnership is a key component of the WHO Comprehensive Mental Health Plan 2013-2030. In the SSA context, it is crucial that all important stakeholders collaborate to achieve a comprehensive and well-coordinated response to the implementation of DMHI in mental health services (34). Collaboration would also ensure that all vital stakeholders, such as developers of DMHI, policymakers, researchers, and service providers, are held accountable and fully understand the role they play in improving access to mental health services with DMHI.

Effective collaboration can be practically done by creating a dedicated organisation or body for DMHI either within national health authorities, units, or in regional formats that would allow the establishment of a formal and strong communication process among stakeholders with a meaningful structure (163-165). This would set the platform for sharing knowledge among a wide range of stakeholders, including experts and policymakers, that would ensure that the best methods and policies are established for efficient DMHI implementation (163-165).

5.5 Research Implications

Further investigations are necessary to gather more accurate deductions of the feasibility and affordability of various DMHI, particularly in larger integration into mental health services. This

review highlighted the crucial significance of the link between the design of DMHI, practical knowledge about DMHI use by service providers, and the suitability of these services to meet patients' mental health needs. This discovery should stimulate more investigation to enhance collaboration and the development of DMHI that prioritises the needs of service users. The findings from this review further emphasise the pressing need to broaden research on the various ways that the development and design of DMHI can adequately navigate the significant barriers to implementation and utilisation of these interventions.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION

6.1 Summarising Synopsis

Undoubtedly, from the analysis of findings of the review, DMHI can substantially transform and improve access to mental health services in SSA. However, there is no sufficient evidence to comprehensively back this assertion in the context of SSA. While DMHI clearly has many beneficial roles that not only improve the symptoms for individuals with mental disorders, DMHI can also improve the quality and accessibility of mental health services. The barriers and obstacles that impede the implementation and utilisation of DMHI are very also significant, and the prevalent socioeconomic circumstances in SSA create considerable doubt on the feasibility and sustainability of achieving the optimal benefits of DMHI in this region.

The interplay of complex factors and sparse data on nationwide adoption of DMHI may indicate the unreadiness of many healthcare systems to integrate and utilise DHMI. Despite the numerous challenges, DMHI, if properly implemented with best practices and strategies, presents the best method to increase access to mental health services in the immediate future and long term in SSA.

6.2 Examination of the Study's Strengths and Limitations.

Despite this review generating enlightening analytical insights, it is important to acknowledge some limitations that may necessitate additional examinations. The methodological approach employed in this study was a mixed methods systematic review, which involved the comprehensive synthesis of data from different study types to address the research question.

I selected this approach because of its validity and extensiveness to evaluate complex concepts such as access. The use of the JBI MMSR guidelines allowed me to easily transform data from different study types, which enabled the categorisation of the findings from included studies into primary themes and sub-themes, which enhanced the comprehension of the data. To further address concerns about any inadequacy with data from different study types, I

utilised the healthcare access framework to guide the selection of the different study types, minimising bias, which is a significant strength of this review.

Despite time restrictions to complete this project, I did not limit articles during the database search by language and conducted an extensive search of English and non-English publications, which ensured comprehensive data for a very thorough analysis. However, the time restrictions also prevented an extensive search of grey literature, which may have excluded some important evidence. Furthermore, due to my limited experience with mixed methods systematic reviews, it may have been beneficial to increase the number of reviewers to offset my limited expertise. However, my supervisor's vast experience with systematic reviews was very enlightening and provided extremely important guidance. Ultimately, the research aims, questions, and objectives were successfully evaluated, and this study enhances the body of evidence on improving access to mental health services with DMHI in SSA and beyond.

REFERENCES

1. GBD 2019 Mental Disorders Collaborators. Global, regional, and national burden of 12 mental disorders in 204 countries and territories, 1990–2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Lancet Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2022 Jan [cited 2024 Jun 6];9(2):137–50. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366\(21\)00395-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366(21)00395-3)
2. Moitra M, Owens S, Hailemariam M, Wilson KS, Mensa-Kwao A, Gonese G, et al. Global mental health: where we are and where we are going. *Curr Psychiatry Rep* [Internet]. 2023 May [cited 2024 Jun 2];25(7):301–11. Available from: <https://www.doi.org/10.1007/s11920-023-01426-8>
3. Wainberg ML, Scorza P, Shultz JM, Helpman L, Mootz JJ, Johnson KA, et al. Challenges and opportunities in global mental health: a research-to-practice perspective. *Curr Psychiatry Rep* [Internet]. 2017 Apr [cited 2024 Jun 2];19: Article number 28. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11920-017-0780-z>
4. World Health Organization. Mental health [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-health-strengthening-our-response>
5. Bolton P, West J, Whitney C, Jordans MJ, Bass J, Thornicroft G, et al. Expanding mental health services in low- and middle-income countries: a task-shifting framework for delivery of comprehensive, collaborative, and community-based care. *Global Ment Health (Camb)* [Internet]. 2023 Feb [cited 2024 Jun 2];10: Article number e16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1017/gmh.2023.5>
6. Knifton L, Inglis G. Poverty and mental health: policy, practice and research implications. *BJPsych Bull* [Internet]. 2020 Oct [cited 2024 Jun 6];44(5):193–6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjb.2020.78>
- 7 The World Bank. Africa overview [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 9]. Available from: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/region/afr/overview>
8. Marbin D, Gutwinski S, Schreiter S, Heinz A. Perspectives in poverty and mental health. *Front Public Health* [Internet]. 2022 Aug [cited 2024 Jun 9];10: Article number 975482. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.975482>
9. Ridley M, Rao G, Schilbach F, Patel V. Poverty, depression, and anxiety: causal evidence and mechanisms. *Science* [Internet]. 2020 Dec [cited 2024 Jun 9];370: Article number 1289. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aay0214>

10. World Bank. Data for low income, sub-Saharan Africa [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Jun 13]. Available from: <https://data.worldbank.org/?locations=ZG-XM>
11. Østergaard ML, Aponte-Canencio DM, Ortiz BY, Botero VJ, Modvig SJ, Brasholt M. Vulnerability factors in conflict-related mental health. *Med Confl Surviv* [Internet]. 2023 Jan [cited 2024 Jun 9];39(1):63–80. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13623699.2022.2156232>
12. Charlson F, Ommeren MV, Flaxman A, Cornett J, Whiteford H, Saxena S. New WHO prevalence estimates of mental disorders in conflict settings: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet* [Internet]. 2019 Jul [cited 2024 Jun 9];394(10194):240–8. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(19\)30934-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(19)30934-1)
13. World Health Organization. Barriers to mental health care in Africa [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://www.afro.who.int/news/barriers-mental-health-care-africa#:~:text=Mental%20healthcare%20for%20people%20living>
14. Wondimagegn D, Pain C, Seifu N, Cartmill C, Alemu AS, Whitehead CR. Reimagining global mental health in Africa. *BMJ Glob Health* [Internet]. 2023 Sep [cited 2024 Jun 2];8: Article number e013232. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2023-013232>
15. United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, World Health Organization. Mental health a human right, but only 1 psychiatrist per 1,000,000 people in sub-Saharan Africa – UNICEF/WHO [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://www.unicef.org/esa/press-releases/mental-health-a-human-right>
16. Nicholas A, Joshua O, Elizabeth O. Accessing mental health services in Africa: current state, efforts, challenges and recommendation. *Ann Med Surg* [Internet]. 2022 Sep [cited 2024 Jun 9];81: Article number 104421. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2022.104421>
17. Omigbodun O, Oyeboode F. Contemporary issues in mental health care in sub-Saharan Africa [Internet]. Ibadan: Bookbuilders Editions Africa; 2017 [cited 2024 Jun 9]. 266p. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvhn09vq>
18. Meffert SM, Lawhorn C, Ongeru L, Bukusi E, Campbell HR, Goosby E, et al. Scaling up public mental health care in sub-Saharan Africa: insights from infectious disease. *Glob Ment Health (Camb)* [Internet]. 2021 Nov [cited 2024 Jun 9]; 8: Article number e41. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1017/gmh.2021.41>

- 19 Liu M, Schueller SM. Moving evidence-based mental health interventions into practice: implementation of digital mental health interventions. *Curr Treat Options Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2023 Oct [cited 2024 Jun 2]; 10 (4):333–45. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40501-023-00298-2>
20. Kim J, Aryee LM, Bang H, Prajogo SE, Choi YK, Hoch JS, et al. Effectiveness of digital mental health tools to reduce depressive and anxiety symptoms in low- and middle-income countries: systematic review and meta-analysis. *JMIR Ment Health* [Internet]. 2022 Sep [cited 2024 Jun 2];10: Article number e43066. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/43066>
21. Patel V, Fancourt D, Furukawa TA, Kola L. Reimagining the journey to recovery: the COVID-19 pandemic and global mental health. *PLoS Med* [Internet]. 2023 Apr [cited 2024 Jun 2];20: Article number e1004224. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1004224>
22. Zangani C, Ostinelli EG, Smith KA, Hong JS, Macdonald O, Reen G, et al. Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the global delivery of mental health services and telemental health: systematic review. *JMIR Ment Health* [Internet]. 2022 Aug [cited 2024 Jun 2]; 9: Article Number e38600. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/38600>
23. Dzinamarira T, Iradukunda PG, Saramba E, Gashema P, Moyo E, Mangezi W, et al. COVID-19 and mental health services in sub-Saharan Africa: a critical literature review. *Compr Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2024 May [cited 2024 Jun 2];131: Article number 152465. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comppsy.2024.152465>
24. World Bank. Digital transformation drives development in Africa [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/results/2024/01/18/digital-transformation-drives-development-in-afe-afw-africa>
25. United States Agency for International Development. Digital development in sub-Saharan Africa mapping findings report [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: https://files.digitalfrontiersdai.com/media/documents/DD_Sub-Saharan_Mapping_17APR23.pdf
26. Harty S, Enrique A, Akkol-Solakoglu S, Adegoke A, Farrell H, Connon G, et al. Implementing digital mental health interventions at scale: one-year evaluation of a national digital CBT service in Ireland. *Int J Ment Health Syst* [Internet]. 2023 Oct [cited 2024 Aug 14];17: Article number 29. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13033-023-00592-9>

27. Cross SP, Nicholas J, Bell IH, Mangelsdorf S, Valentine L, Thompson A, et al. Integrating digital interventions with clinical practice in youth mental health services. *Australasian Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2023 Jun [cited 2024 Aug 14];31(3):302–5. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/10398562231169365>
28. Smith K, Blease C, Faurholt-Jepsen M, Firth J, Van Daele T, Moreno C, et al. Digital mental health: challenges and next steps. *BMJ Ment Health* [Internet]. 2023 May [cited 2024 Jun 9];26: 1-7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjment-2023-300670>
29. Kipruto H, Muneene D, Droti B, Jepchumba V, Okeibunor CJ, Nabyonga-Orem J, et al. Use of digital health interventions in sub-Saharan Africa for health systems strengthening over the last 10 years: a scoping review protocol. *Front Digit Health* [Internet]. 2022 May [cited 2024 Aug 14];4: Article number 874251. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdqth.2022.874251>
30. World Health Organization. Mental health [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: https://www.who.int/health-topics/mental-health#tab=tab_1
31. World Health Organization. Mental disorders [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-disorders>
32. World Health Organization. International Classification of Diseases 11th Revision ICD-11 [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://icd.who.int/en>
33. World Health Organization. SDG Target 3.4 noncommunicable diseases and mental health: by 2030, reduce by one third premature mortality from non-communicable diseases through prevention and treatment and promote mental health and well-being [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/topics/indicator-groups/indicator-group-details/GHO/sdg-target-3.4-noncommunicable-diseases-and-mental-health>
34. World Health Organization. Comprehensive Mental Health Action Plan 2013-2030 [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2024 Jun 6]. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/345301/9789240031029-eng.pdf?sequence=1>
35. Roberts T, Esponda GM, Torre C, Pillai P, Cohen A, Burgess RA. Reconceptualising the treatment gap for common mental disorders: a fork in the road for global mental health? *BJ Psych* [Internet]. 2022 Feb [cited 2024 Jun 6];221(3):553–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.2021.221>

36. Rathod S, Pinninti N, Irfan M, Gorczynski P, Rathod P, Gega L, et al. Mental health service provision in low- and middle-income countries. *Health Serv Insights* [Internet]. 2017 Jan [cited 2024 Jun 6]; 10. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1178632917694350>
37. World Health Organization. World Mental Health Day 2022 [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 6]. Available from: <https://www.afro.who.int/regional-director/speeches-messages/world-mental-health-day-2022>
38. World Health Organization. Mental Health ATLAS 2020 [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2024 Jun 13]. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/345946/9789240036703-eng.pdf?sequence=1>
39. World Health Organization. Guidance on community mental health services: promoting person-centred and rights-based approaches [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2024 Jun 6]. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/341648/9789240025707-eng.pdf?sequence=1>
40. Rebello TJ, Marques A, Gureje O, Pike KM. Innovative strategies for closing the mental health treatment gap globally. *Curr Opin Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2014 Jul [cited 2024 Jun 6];27(4):308–14. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1097/ycp.000000000000068>
41. World Health Organization. Global strategy on digital health 2020-2025 [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2024 Jun 6]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/documents/gS4dhdaa2a9f352b0445bafbc79ca799dce4d.pdf>
42. Taher R, Hsu CW, Fialho C, Hampshire C, Heaysman C, Stahl D, et al. The safety of digital mental health interventions: a systematic review and recommendations. *JMIR Ment Health* [Internet]. 2023 Oct [cited 2024 Jun 8];10: Article number e47433. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/47433>
43. Park SY, Sigmon NC, Boeldt D. A framework for the implementation of digital mental health interventions: the Importance of feasibility and acceptability research. *Cureus* [Internet]. 2022 Sep [cited 2024 Jun 8];14: Article number e29329. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.29329>
44. Nelson BW, Peiper NC, Forman-Hoffman VL. Digital mental health interventions as stand-alone vs. augmented treatment as usual. *BMC Public Health* [Internet]. 2024 Apr [cited 2024 Jun 8];24: Article number 969. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-18412-1>

45. Riadi I, Kervin L, Dhillon S, Teo K, Churchill R, Card KG, et al. Digital interventions for depression and anxiety in older adults: a systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *Lancet Healthy Longev* [Internet]. 2022 Aug [cited 2024 Jun 8];3(8): e558–71. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-7568\(22\)00121-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-7568(22)00121-0)
46. Tng GY, Koh J, Soh XC, Majeed NM, Hartanto A. Efficacy of digital mental health interventions for PTSD symptoms: a systematic review of meta-analyses. *J Affect Disord* [Internet]. 2024 Apr [cited 2024 Jun 8]; 357:23–36. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2024.04.074>
47. World Health Organization. WHO digital mental health intervention effective in reducing depression among Syrian refugees in Lebanon [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 8]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/feature-stories/detail/who-digital-mental-health-intervention-effective-in-reducing-depression-among-syrian-refugees-in-lebanon#:~:text=It%20found%20that%20people%20who>
48. Ghosh A, Cherian RJ, Wagle S, Sharma P, Kannan KR, Bajpai A, et al. An unguided, computerized cognitive behavioral therapy intervention (TreadWill) in a lower middle-income country: pragmatic randomized controlled trial. *J Med Internet Res* [Internet]. 2023 Apr [cited 2024 Aug 14];25: Article number e41005. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/41005>
49. Gonsalves PP, Hodgson ES, Bhat B, Sharma R, Jambhale A, Michelson D, et al. App-based guided problem-solving intervention for adolescent mental health: a pilot cohort study in Indian schools. *Evid Based Ment Health* [Internet]. 2020 Nov [cited 2024 Aug 9];24(1):11–8. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1136/ebmental-2020-300194>
50. World Bank. Sub-Saharan Africa data [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Jun 9]. Available from: <https://data.worldbank.org/country/ZG>
51. Migration Policy Institute. Africa (sub-Saharan) [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2024 Jun 9]. Available from: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/regions/africa-sub-saharan>
52. Amu H, Dzenu MW, Baku ST, Naboare D, Charles-Unadike VO, Boateng LA, et al. Addressing mental health challenges and non-communicable diseases in sub-Saharan Africa: an analysis from health systems approach. *Preventive Medicine: Research & Reviews* [Internet]. 2024 Jan-Feb [cited 2024 Jun 9];1(1):21-4. Available from: https://doi.org/10.4103/PMRR.PMRR_57_23

53. World Health Organization. Universal health coverage (UHC) [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 9]. Available from: [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/universal-health-coverage-\(uhc\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/universal-health-coverage-(uhc))
54. Centre for Global Mental Health. Mental health in Africa: innovation and investment [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2024 Jun 9]. Available from: <https://www.centreforglobalmentalhealth.org/news/mental-health-in-africa-innovation-and-investment>
55. Ebeye T, Lee H. Down the brain drain: a rapid review exploring physician emigration from West Africa. *Glob Health Res Policy* [Internet]. 2023 Jun [cited 2024 Jun 9];8: Article number 23. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41256-023-00307-0>
56. Poppe A, Jirovsky E, Blacklock C, Laxmikanth P, Moosa S, Maeseneer JD, et al. Why sub-Saharan African health workers migrate to European countries that do not actively recruit: a qualitative study post-migration. *Glob Health Action* [Internet]. 2014 May [cited 2024 Jun 9];7: Article number 24071. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v7.24071>
57. Abi S. Brain drain in Africa's health-care sector [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Jun 9]. Available from: <https://www.dandc.eu/en/article/medical-professionals-are-emigrating-africa-because-catastrophic-conditions-health-care>
58. Gureje O, Seedat S, Kola L, Appiah-Poku J, Othieno C, Harris B, et al. Partnership for mental health development in sub-Saharan Africa (PaM-D): a collaborative initiative for research and capacity building. *Epidemiol Psychiatr Sci* [Internet]. 2019 Aug [cited 2024 Jun 9];28(4):389–96. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s2045796018000707>
59. Vaishnav M, Javed A, Gupta S, Kumar V, Vaishnav P, Kumar A, et al. Stigma towards mental illness in Asian nations and low-and-middle-income countries, and comparison with high-income countries: a literature review and practice implications. *Indian J Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2023 Oct [cited 2024 Jun 13];65(10):995–1011. Available from: https://doi.org/10.4103/indianjpsychiatry.indianjpsychiatry_667_23
60. Ahad AA, Sanchez-Gonzalez M, Junquera P. Understanding and addressing mental health stigma across cultures for improving psychiatric care: a narrative review. *Cureus* [Internet]. 2023 May [cited 2024 Jun 13];15: Article number e39549. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.39549>
61. Muhorakeye O, Biracyaza E. Exploring barriers to mental health services utilization at Kabutare District Hospital of Rwanda: perspectives from patients. *Front in Psychol* [Internet].

2021 Mar [cited 2024 Jun 9];12: Article number 638377. Available from:

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.638377>

62. Ogunwale A, Fadipe B, Bifarin O. Indigenous mental healthcare and human rights abuses in Nigeria: the role of cultural syntonicity and stigmatization. *Front Public Health* [Internet]. 2023 Jun [cited 2024 Jun 9];11: Article number 1122396. Available from:

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1122396>

63. Ozota GO, Sabastine RN, Uduji FC, Okonkwo VC. Nigeria mental health law: challenges and implications for mental health services. *S Afr J Psychiatr* [Internet]. 2024 Apr [cited 2024 Jun 14];30: Article number 2134. Available from:

<https://sajp.org.za/index.php/sajp/article/view/2134>

64. Susuman SA. Mental health issues and policy in sub-Saharan Africa: a view from Cape Town to Cairo. *Int J Healthc Med Sci* [Internet]. 2018 July [cited 2024 Jun 9];3(3):59–66.

Available from: <https://doi.org/10.20469/ijhms.3.30001-3>

65. Levesque JF, Harris MF, Russell G. Patient-centred access to health care: conceptualising access at the interface of health systems and populations. *Int J Equity Health* [Internet]. 2013 Mar [cited 2024 Jun 13];12: Article number 18. Available from:

<https://doi.org/10.1186/1475-9276-12-18>

66. Cu A, Meister S, Lefebvre B, Ridde V. Assessing healthcare access using the Levesque’s conceptual framework– a scoping review. *Int J Equity Health* [Internet]. 2021 May [cited 2024 Jun 13];20: Article number 116. Available from:

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-021-01416-3>

67. Snyder H. Literature review as a research methodology: an overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research* [Internet]. 2019 Nov [cited 2024 Jun 13];104(1):333–9.

Available from: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusres.2019.07.039>

68. Stern C, Lizarondo L, Carrier J, Godfrey C, Rieger K, Salmond S, et al. Methodological guidance for the conduct of mixed methods systematic reviews. *JBI Evid Synth* [Internet].

2020 Oct [cited 2024 Jul 7];18(10):2108-18 Available from: <https://doi.org/10.11124/jbisrir-d-19-00169>

69. Newman M, Gough D. Systematic reviews in educational research: methodology, perspectives and application [Internet]. Germany; Springer VS, Wiesbaden; 2020 [cited 2024 Jun 27];3–22p. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-27602-7_1

70. Ganeshkumar P, Gopalakrishnan S. Systematic reviews and meta-analysis: understanding the best evidence in primary healthcare. *J Family Med Prim Care* [Internet]. 2013 Jan-Mar [cited 2024 Jun 27];2(1):9–14. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.4103/2249-4863.109934>
71. Smith KA, Cipriani A, Geddes JR. The usefulness and interpretation of systematic reviews. *BJPsych Advances* [Internet]. 2016 Mar [cited 2024 Jun 27];22(2):132–41. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1192/apt.bp.114.013128>
72. Frandsen TF, Nielsen MF, Lindhardt CL, Eriksen MB. Using the full PICO model as a search tool for systematic reviews resulted in lower recall for some PICO elements. *J Clin Epidemiol* [Internet]. 2020 Nov [cited 2024 Aug 4]; 127:69–75. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2020.07.005>
73. Hariton E, Locascio JJ. Randomised controlled trials - the gold standard for effectiveness research. *BJOG* [Internet]. 2018 Dec [cited 2024 Aug 4];125(13):1716. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-0528.15199>
74. Lewin S, Glenton C, Oxman AD. Use of qualitative methods alongside randomised controlled trials of complex healthcare interventions: methodological study. *BMJ* [Internet]. 2009 Sep [cited 2024 Aug 4]; 339: Article number b3496. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.b3496>
75. Waddington HS, Villar PF, Valentine JC. Can non-randomised studies of interventions provide unbiased effect estimates? a systematic review of internal replication studies. *Eval Rev* [Internet]. 2023 Jun [cited 2024 Aug 5]; 47(3):563-93. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0193841x221116721>
76. Kechagias EP, Papadopoulos GA, Rokai I. Evaluating the impact of digital health interventions on workplace health outcomes: a systematic review. *Adm Sci* [Internet]. 2024 Jun [cited 2024 Jul 7];14: Article number 131. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci14060131>
77. Doherty JL, Owen MJ. Genomic insights into the overlap between psychiatric disorders: implications for research and clinical practice. *Genome Medicine* [Internet]. 2014 [cited 2024 Aug 28];6:Article number 29. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.14476.2>
78. Greene MC, Yangchen T, Lehner T, Sullivan PF, Pato CN, McIntosh A, et al. The epidemiology of psychiatric disorders in Africa: a scoping review. *Lancet Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2021 Aug [cited 2024 Aug 1];8(8):717–31. Available from:

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366\(21\)00009-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366(21)00009-2)

79. Hong QN, Fàbregues S, Bartlett G, Boardman F, Cargo M, Dagenais P, et al. The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) version 2018 for information professionals and researchers. *Education for Information* [Internet]. 2018 Nov [cited 2024 Aug 5];34(4):285–91. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3233/EFI-180221>

80. Page MJ, Moher D, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* [Internet]. 2021 Mar [cited 2024 Jun 27];372: Article number 160. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n160>

81. Musyimi CW, Mutiso VN, Haji ZR, Nandoya ES, Ndeti DM. Mobile based mhGAP-IG depression screening in Kenya. *Community Ment Health J* [Internet]. 2016 Nov [cited 2024 Jul 18]; 54:84–91. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007%2Fs10597-016-0072-9>

82. Gericke F, Ebert DD, Breet E, Auerbach RP, Bantjes J. A qualitative study of university students' experience of internet-based CBT for depression. *Couns Psychother Res* [Internet]. 2021 Dec [cited 2024 Jul 18];21(4):792–804. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/capr.12465>

83. Hunt X, Jivan DC, Naslund JA, Breet E, Bantjes J. South African university students' experiences of online group cognitive behavioural therapy: implications for delivering digital mental health interventions to young people. *Glob Ment Health (Camb)* [Internet]. 2023 July [cited 2024 Jul 18];10: Article number e45. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1017/gmh.2023.39>

84. Dambi J, Norman C, Doukani A, Potgieter S, Turner J, Musesengwa R, et al. A digital mental health intervention (Inuka) for common mental health disorders in Zimbabwean adults in response to the COVID-19 pandemic: a feasibility and acceptability pilot study. *JMIR Ment Health* [Internet]. 2022 Oct [cited 2024 Jul 18]; 9: Article number e37968. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/37968>

85. Munthali-Mulemba S, Figge CJ, Metz K, Kane JC, Skavenski S, Mwenge M, et al. Experiences and perceptions of telephone-delivery of the Common Elements Treatment Approach for mental health needs among young people in Zambia during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Front Public Health* [Internet]. 2022 Oct [cited 2024 Jul 18];10: Article number 906509. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.906509>

86. Mulungu C, Mindu T, Mulungu K. Effectiveness of online counselling during COVID-19 in Zambia: a clients' and therapists' perspective. *BMC Psychol* [Internet]. 2024 Mar [cited 2024 Jul 18];12: Article number 132. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-024-01614-y>
87. Hassem T. Evaluating the efficacy of an online depression screening tool in South Africa: A pilot study. *S Afr J Psychiatr* [Internet]. 2022 Feb [cited 2024 Jul 18];28: Article number 168. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.4102>
88. Adewuya AO, Momodu O, Olibamoyo O, Adegbaaju A, Adesoji O, Adegbokun A. The effectiveness and acceptability of mobile telephone adherence support for management of depression in the Mental Health in Primary Care (MeHPriC) project, Lagos, Nigeria: a pilot cluster randomised controlled trial. *J Affect Disord* [Internet]. 2019 Jun [cited 2024 Jul 18]; 253:118–25. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2019.04.025>
89. Chory A, Callen G, Nyandiko W, Njoroge T, Ashimosi C, Aluoch J, et al. A pilot study of a mobile intervention to support mental health and adherence among adolescents living with HIV in Western Kenya. *AIDS Behav* [Internet]. 2022 Jul [cited 2024 Jul 18]; 26:232–42. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-021-03376-9>
90. Sibeko G, Temmingh H, Mall S, Williams-Ashman P, Thornicroft G, Susser ES, et al. Improving adherence in mental health service users with severe mental illness in South Africa: a pilot randomized controlled trial of a treatment partner and text message intervention vs. treatment as usual. *BMC Res Notes* [Internet]. 2017 Nov [cited 2024 Jul 18];10: Article number 584. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-017-2915-z>
91. Ben-Zeev D, Larsen A, Attah DA, Obeng K, Beaulieu A, Asafo SM, et al. Combining mHealth technology and pharmacotherapy to improve mental health outcomes and reduce human rights abuses in West Africa: intervention field trial. *JMIR Ment Health* [Internet]. 2024 Mar [cited 2024 Jul 20];11: Article number 53096. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/53096>
92. Constant D, de Tolly K, Harries J, Myer L. Mobile phone messages to provide support to women during the home phase of medical abortion in South Africa: a randomised controlled trial. *Contraception* [Internet]. 2014 Sep [cited 2024 Aug 5];90(3):226–33. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.contraception.2014.04.009>
93. Sudhinaraset M, Landrian A, Cotter SY, Golub G, Opot J, Seefeld CA, et al. Improving stigma and psychosocial outcomes among post-abortion Kenyan women attending private clinics: a randomized controlled trial of a person-centered mobile phone-based intervention.

PLoS One [Internet]. 2022 Jun [cited 2024 Aug 5];17: Article number e0270637. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0270637>

94. Verkijika SF, De Wet L. Using a brain-computer interface (BCI) in reducing math anxiety: evidence from South Africa. *Comput Educ* [Internet]. 2015 Feb [cited 2024 Aug 5]; 81:113–22. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.10.002>

95. Thomas IF, Lawani AO, James BO. Effect of short message service reminders on clinic attendance among outpatients with psychosis at a psychiatric hospital in Nigeria. *Psychiatr Serv* [Internet]. 2017 Jan [cited 2024 Aug 5];68(1):75–80. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ps.201500514>

96. Osborn TL, Rodriguez M, Wasil AR, Venturo-Conerly KE, Gan J, Alemu RG, et al. Single-session digital intervention for adolescent depression, anxiety, and well-being: outcomes of a randomized controlled trial with Kenyan adolescents. *J Consult Clin Psychol* [Internet]. 2020 Jul [cited 2024 Aug 5];88(7):657–68. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/ccp0000505>

97. du Bois N, Bigirimana AD, Korik A, Kéthina LG, Rutembesa E, Mutabaruka J, et al. Neurofeedback with low-cost, wearable electroencephalography (EEG) reduces symptoms in chronic post-traumatic stress disorder. *J Affect Disord* [Internet]. 2021 Dec [cited 2024 Aug 5]; 295:1319–34. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2021.08.071>

98. Doukani A, van Dalen R, Valev H, Njenga A, Sera F, Chibanda D. A community health volunteer delivered problem-solving therapy mobile application based on the Friendship Bench “Inuka Coaching” in Kenya: a pilot cohort study. *Global Ment Health (Camb)* [Internet]. 2021 Sep [cited 2024 Aug 5];10: Article number e9. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1017/gmh.2021.3>

99. Ofoegbu TO, Asogwa U, Otu MS, Ibenegbu C, Muhammed A, Eze B. Efficacy of guided internet-assisted intervention on depression reduction among educational technology students of Nigerian universities. *Medicine (Baltimore)* [Internet]. 2020 Feb [cited 2024 Aug 5];99(6): 18774. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1097/md.00000000000018774>

100. Bantjes J, Hunt X, Pim Cuijpers, Kazdin AE, Kennedy CJ, Luedtke A, et al. Comparative effectiveness of remote digital gamified and group CBT skills training interventions for anxiety and depression among college students: results of a three-arm randomised controlled trial. *Behav Res Ther* [Internet]. 2024 Jul [cited 2024 Aug 5];178: Article number 104554. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brat.2024.104554>

101. Olisaeloka L, Udokanma E, Ashraf A. Psychosocial interventions for depression among young people in sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Ment Health Syst* [Internet]. 2024 Jun 22 [cited 2024 Aug 26];18: Article number 24. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13033-024-00642-w>
102. Omigbodun OO, Ryan GK, Fasoranti B, Chibanda D, Esliker R, Sefasi A, et al. Reprioritising global mental health: psychoses in sub-Saharan Africa. *Int J Ment Health Syst* [Internet]. 2023 Mar [cited 2024 Aug 5];17: Article number 16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13033-023-00574-x>
103. Gbadamosi IT, Henneh IT, Aluko OM, Yawson EO, Fokoua AR, Koomson A, et al. Depression in sub-Saharan Africa. *IBRO Neurosci Rep* [Internet]. 2022 Jun [cited 2024 Aug 5]; 12:309–22. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibneur.2022.03.005>
104. Ierardi E, Bottini M, Crugnola RC. Effectiveness of an online versus face-to-face psychodynamic counselling intervention for university students before and during the COVID-19 period. *BMC Psychol* [Internet]. 2022 Feb [cited 2024 Aug 18];10: Article number 35. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-022-00742-7>
105. Huang Y, Loux T, Huang X, Feng X. The relationship between chronic diseases and mental health: a cross-sectional study. *Ment Health Prev* [Internet]. 2023 Dec [cited 2024 Aug 12]; 32: Article number 200307. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhp.2023.200307>
106. Doherty AM, Gaughran F. The interface of physical and mental health. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol* [Internet]. 2014 Feb [cited 2024 Aug 12]; 49:673–82. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-014-0847-7>
107. Gouda HN, Charlson F, Sorsdahl K, Ahmadzada S, Ferrari AJ, Erskine H, et al. Burden of non-communicable diseases in sub-Saharan Africa, 1990–2017: results from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *Lancet Glob Health* [Internet]. 2019 Oct [cited 2024 Aug 18];7(10): e1375–87. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2214-109x\(19\)30374-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2214-109x(19)30374-2)
108. Rodríguez-Rivas ME, Cangas AJ, Cariola LA, Varela JJ, Valdebenito S. Innovative technology-based interventions to reduce stigma toward people with mental illness: systematic review and meta-analysis. *JMIR Serious Games* [Internet]. 2022 Apr-Jun [cited 2024 Jul 24];10: Article number e35099. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/35099>
109. Kpanake L. Cultural concepts of the person and mental health in Africa. *Transcultural Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2018 Apr [cited 2024 Jul 24];55(2):198–218. Available from:

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1363461517749435>

110. Ogunkola IO, Adebisi YA, Imo UF, Odey GO, Esu E, Lucero-Prisno DE. Rural communities in Africa should not be forgotten in responses to COVID-19. *Int J Health Plann Manage* [Internet]. 2020 Nov [cited 2024 Jul 24];35(6):1302–5. Available from:

<https://doi.org/10.1002/hpm.3039>

111. Robertson LJ. The impact of urbanization on mental health service provision: a Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa and Africa focus. *Curr Opin Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2019 May [cited 2024 Jul 24];32(3):224–31. Available from:

<https://doi.org/10.1097/yco.0000000000000495>

112. Hadjiat Y. Healthcare inequity and digital health—a bridge for the divide, or further erosion of the chasm? *PLOS Digit Health* [Internet]. 2023 Jun [cited 2024 Aug 18];2: Article number e0000268. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000268>

113. Naslund JA, Aschbrenner KA, Araya R, Marsch LA, Unützer J, Patel V, et al. Digital technology for treating and preventing mental disorders in low-income and middle-income countries: a narrative review of the literature. *Lancet Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2017 Jun [cited 2024 Jul 24];4(6):486–500. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366\(17\)30096-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366(17)30096-2)

114. Gwaka LT, May J, Tucker W. Towards low-cost community networks in rural communities: the impact of context using the case study of Beitbridge, Zimbabwe. *Electr J Inf Sys Dev* [Internet]. 2018 May [cited 2024 Jul 24];84(2): Article number e12029. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/isd2.12029>

115. Ousmanne M. Africa: The cost of internet is 5 times higher than the global average [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Jul 24]. Available from:

<https://powersofafrica.com/article/716/africa-the-cost-of-internet-is-5-times-higher-than-the-global-average>

116. Mukosa F, Mweemba B. The digital divide hindering e-learning in Zambia. *IJSRG* [Internet]. 2019 Jul [cited 2024 Jul 24]; 2:860–5. Available from:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7421850>

117. Admass WS, Diro AA, Munaye YY. Cyber security: state of the art, challenges and future directions. *Cyber Security and Applications* [Internet]. 2023 Oct [cited 2024 Aug 18]; 2: Article number 100031. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csa.2023.100031>

118. International Telecommunication Union. Global Cybersecurity Index 2020 [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2024 Aug 18]. Available from: <https://www.itu.int/epublications/publication/D-STR-GCI.01-2021-HTM-E>
119. Tegegne MD, Tilahun B, Mamuye A, Kerie H, Nurhussien F, Zemen E, et al. Digital literacy level and associated factors among health professionals in a referral and teaching hospital: an implication for future digital health systems implementation. *Front Public Health* [Internet]. 2023 Apr [cited 2024 Jul 24];11: Article number 1130894. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1130894>
120. Motiwala F, Ezezika O. Barriers to scaling health technologies in sub-Saharan Africa: lessons from Ethiopia, Nigeria, and Rwanda. *Afr J Sci Technol Innov Dev* [Internet]. 2022 Nov [cited 2024 Jul 24]; 14(7): 1788-97 Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/20421338.2021.1985203>
121. Do4africa. Digital literacy in Africa [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2024 Jul 24]. Available from: <https://www.do4africa.org/en/digital-literacy-in-africa/>
122. Lipschitz JM, Pike CK, Hogan TP, Murphy SA, Burdick KE. The engagement problem: a review of engagement with digital mental health interventions and recommendations for a path forward. *Curr Treat Options Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2023 Aug [cited 2024 Jun 9]; 10:119–35. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40501-023-00297-3>
123. Borghouts J, Eikey E, Mark G, De Leon C, Schueller SM, Schneider M, et al. Barriers to and facilitators of user engagement with digital mental health interventions: systematic review. *J Med Internet Res* [Internet]. 2021 Mar [cited 2024 Jul 24];23: Article number e24387. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/24387>
124. Italian institute for International Political Studies. Is poverty growing again in sub-Saharan Africa? trends and measures [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Jul 24]. Available from: <https://www.ispionline.it/en/publication/is-poverty-growing-again-in-sub-saharan-africa-trends-and-measures-137866>
125. United Nations Statistics Division. End poverty in all its forms everywhere [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Jul 24]. Available from: <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2019/goal-01/>
126. World Economic Forum. As young Africans push to be online, data cost stands in the way [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Jul 24]. Available from: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/06/as-young-africans-push-to-be-online-data-cost-stands-in-the-way/>

127. García-Escribano M. Low internet access driving inequality [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2024 Jul 24]. Available from: <https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2020/06/29/low-internet-access-driving-inequality>
128. Mostert CM, Nesic O, Udeh-Momoh C, Khan M, Thesen T, Bosire E, et al. Who should pay the bill for the mental health crisis in Africa? Public health Pract [Internet]. 2024 Jun [cited 2024 Jul 24];7: Article number 100458. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhip.2023.100458>
129. Philippe TJ, Sikder N, Jackson A, Koblanski ME, Liow E, Pilarinos A, et al. Digital health interventions for delivery of mental health care: systematic and comprehensive meta-review. JMIR Ment Health [Internet]. 2022 May [cited 2024 Aug 19]; 9: Article number e35159. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/35159>
- 130 Baños RM, Herrero R, Vara MD. What is the current and future status of digital mental health interventions? Span J Psychiatry Ment Health [Internet]. 2022 Feb [cited 2024 Aug 19];25: Article number e5. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1017/sjp.2022.2>
131. Marsh McLennan. Digital tools promise much for mental health — but they are not a panacea [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2024 Aug 19]. Available from: <https://www.brinknews.com/digital-tools-promise-much-for-mental-health-but-they-are-not-a-panacea/>
132. Balcombe L, De Leo D. Digital mental health challenges and the horizon ahead for solutions. JMIR Mental Health [Internet]. 2021 Mar [cited 2024 Aug 19];8: Article number e26811. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2196/26811>
133. Babajide A, Ahmad AH, Coleman S. Violent conflicts and state capacity: evidence from sub-Saharan Africa. Journal of Government and Economics [Internet]. 2021 Nov [cited 2021 Dec 12];3: Article number 100019. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jge.2021.100019>
134. International Monetary Fund. How distrust of government by marginalized people fuels conflict in Africa [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 19]. Available from: <https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2024/01/25/how-distrust-of-government-by-marginalized-people-fuels-conflict-in-africa#:~:text=Sub%2DSaharan%20Africa%20suffers%20from>
135. Nirisha PL, Malathesh BC, Kulal N, Harshithaa NR, Ibrahim FA, Suhas S, et al. Impact of technology driven mental health task-shifting for accredited social health activists (ASHAs): results from a randomised controlled trial of two methods of training.

Community Ment Health J [Internet]. 2023 Jan [cited 2024 Aug 19]; 59(1):175–84. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10597-022-00996-w>

136. Naslund JA, Shidhaye R, Patel V. Digital technology for building capacity of nonspecialist health workers for task sharing and scaling up mental health care globally. Harv Rev Psychiatry [Internet]. 2019 May/Jun [cited 2024 Aug 19];27(3):181–92. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1097/hrp.0000000000000217>

137. Petretto DR, Carrogu GP, Gaviano L, Berti R, Pinna M, Petretto DA, et al. Digital determinants of health as a way to address multilevel complex causal model in the promotion of digital health equity and the prevention of digital health inequities: a scoping review. J Public Health Res [Internet]. 2024 Jan [cited 2024 Aug 19];13(1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/22799036231220352>

138. Holst C, Sukums F, Radovanovic D, Ngowi B, Noll J, Winkler AS. Sub-Saharan Africa—the new breeding ground for global digital health. Lancet Digit Health [Internet]. 2020 Apr [cited 2024 Aug 7];2(4): e160–2. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2589-7500\(20\)30027-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2589-7500(20)30027-3)

139. Yankam BM, Amu H, Dowou RH, Nyamen BG, Ubechu SC, et al. Task shifting and task sharing in the health sector in sub-Saharan Africa: evidence, success indicators, challenges, and opportunities. Pan Afr Med J [Internet]. 2023 Sep [cited 2024 Aug 7];46: Article number 11. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2023.46.11.40984>

140. Iwelunmor J, Blackstone S, Veira D, Nwaozuru U, Airhihenbuwa C, Munodawafa D, et al. Toward the sustainability of health interventions implemented in sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review and conceptual framework. Implement Sci [Internet]. 2015 Dec [cited 2024 Aug 7];11: Article number 43. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-016-0392-8>

141 Swartz A, LeFevre AE, Perera S, Kinney MV, George AS. Multiple pathways to scaling up and sustainability: an exploration of digital health solutions in South Africa. Globalization and Health [Internet]. 2021 Jul [cited 2024 Aug 22];17: Article number 77. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-021-00716-1>

142. Stat counter. Mobile operating system market share Africa [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2024 Aug 7]. Available from: <https://gs.statcounter.com/os-market-share/mobile/africa>

143. Abdulqadir IA, Asongu SA. The asymmetric effect of internet access on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. Economic Analysis and Policy [Internet]. 2022 Mar [cited 2024 Aug 7]; 73:44–61. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eap.2021.10.014>

144. Beyene E, Bedemo A, Gebremeskel A. Determinants of digital technology development in sub-Saharan African countries: evidence from panel data analysis. *Energy Inform* [Internet]. 2024 Mar [cited 2024 Aug 19];7: Article number 21. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42162-024-00324-4>
145. Quigley B. Improving connectivity and accelerating economic growth across Africa with new investments [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 20]. Available from: <https://blog.google/intl/en-africa/company-news/improving-connectivity-and-accelerating-economic-growth-across-africa/#:~:text=Africa%27s%20internet%20economy%20has%20the>
146. The GSM Association. Despite improvements, sub-Saharan Africa has the widest usage and coverage gaps worldwide [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 19]. Available from: <https://www.gsma.com/solutions-and-impact/connectivity-for-good/mobile-for-development/blog/despite-improvements-sub-saharan-africa-has-the-widest-usage-and-coverage-gaps-worldwide/#:~:text=Mobile%20technologies%20and%20services%20have,in%202022%2C%20totalling%20%24170%20billion.>
147. Center for Strategic and International Studies. How web-connected is China? [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2024 Aug 7]. Available from: <https://chinapower.csis.org/web-connectedness/#:~:text=In%202015%2C%20the%20State%20Council>
148. Jia L, Nam E, Chun D. Impact of Chinese government subsidies on enterprise innovation: based on a three-dimensional perspective. *Sustainability* [Internet]. 2021 Jan [cited 2024 Aug 7];13: Article number 1288. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13031288>
149. African Union Commission (AUC), Organization for Economic Cooperation Development (OECD). Digital transformation for quality jobs Africa's development dynamics 2021 [Internet]. Addis Ababa/Paris: AUC/OECD Publishing;2021 [cited 2024 Aug 7]. 284p. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1787/0a5c9314-en>
150. Data protection Africa. Mapping the progress (and delays) for data protection in Africa [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Aug 7]. Available from: <https://dataprotection.africa/data-protection-in-africa-progress/>
151. Kshetri N. Cybercrime and cybersecurity in the Global South [Internet]. 2013th edition. London: Palgrave Macmillan ;2013 [cited 2022 Aug 2].152p–70. Available from:

https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137021946_8

152. Positive Technologies. Cybersecurity threatscape of African countries 2022–2023 [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Aug 21]. Available from: <https://www.ptsecurity.com/www-en/analytics/africa-cybersecurity-threatscape-2022-2023/>

153. Ifeanyi-Ajufo N. Cyber governance in Africa: at the crossroads of politics, sovereignty and cooperation. Policy Des Pract [Internet]. 2023 May [cited 2024 Aug 21]; 6:146–59. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2023.2199960>

154. European Council. The general data protection regulation [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 20]. Available from: [https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/data-protection/data-protection-regulation/#:~:text=The%20EU%20general%20data%20protection%20regulation%20\(GDPR\)%20is%20the%20strongest](https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/data-protection/data-protection-regulation/#:~:text=The%20EU%20general%20data%20protection%20regulation%20(GDPR)%20is%20the%20strongest)

155. Breitbarth P. The impact of GDPR one year on. Network Security [Internet]. 2019 Jul [cited 2024 Aug 20];2019(7):11–3. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1353-4858\(19\)30084-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1353-4858(19)30084-4)

156. Amoo OO, Atadoga A, Osasona F, Abrahams OT, Ayinla BS, Farayola OA. GDPR's impact on cybersecurity: a review focusing on USA and European practices. IJSRA Archive [Internet]. 2024 Feb [cited 2024 Aug 20];11(1):1338–47. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijsra.2024.11.1.0220>

157. University of East Anglia. Data protection laws reduced breaches but affected firms' value [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 20]. Available from: <https://www.uea.ac.uk/about/news/article/data-protection-laws-reduced-breaches-but-affected-firms-value>

158. European Council. Cybersecurity in Europe: stronger rules and better protection [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 19]. Available from: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/cybersecurity/>

159. Euronews. Disruptive attacks have doubled in EU, cybersecurity chief says [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 20]. Available from: <https://www.euronews.com/next/2024/05/29/disruptive-attacks-double-in-eu-in-recent-months-cybersecurity-chief-says>

160. IT Governance Europe. Data breaches and cyber attacks in Europe in February 2024 – 50,884,709 records breached [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 20]. Available from: <https://www.itgovernance.eu/blog/en/data-breaches-and-cyber-attacks-in-europe-in-february-2024-50884709-records-breached>
161. World Health Organization. mhGAP Intervention Guide [Internet]. 2016 [cited 2024 Aug 12]. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/250239/9789241549790-eng.pdf?sequence=1>
162. Keynejad R, Spagnolo J, Thornicroft G. WHO mental health gap action programme (mhGAP) intervention guide: updated systematic review on evidence and impact. *Evid Based Ment Health* [Internet]. 2021 Apr [cited 2024 Aug 7];24(3):124–30. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1136/ebmental-2021-300254>
163. Pradier C, Balinska MA, Bailly L. Enhancing multi-sectoral collaboration in health: the open arena for public health as a model for bridging the knowledge-translation gap. *Front Health Serv* [Internet]. 2023 Sep [cited 2024 Aug 19];3: Article number 1216234. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/frhs.2023.1216234>
164. Alhassan JA, Gauvin L, Judge A, Fuller D, Engler-Stringer R, Muhajarine N. Improving health through multisectoral collaboration: enablers and barriers. *Can J Public Health* [Internet]. 2021 Jun [cited 2024 Aug 19];112(6):1059–68. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.17269/s41997-021-00534-3>
165. Salunke S, Lal DK. Multisectoral approach for promoting public health. *Indian J Public Health* [Internet]. 2017 Jul-Sep [cited 2024 Aug 19];61(3):163–8. Available from: https://doi.org/10.4103/ijph.ijph_220_17

APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: SEARCH STRATEGY

Global Health (Ovid) Onsite Access- 144	
1	(intervention* or treat* or therap* or manag* or diagnos* or counsel*).mp. [mp=abstract, title, original title, heading words, cabicodes words]
2	(mental or psych* or anxiety or depress* or Schizophreni* or Ptsd or trauma* or panic or bipolar or paranoia or phobia or OCD or dissociati* or CBT or cognitive behavioral therapy or eye movement desensitization reprocessing or EMDR or relationship-based interventions or RBIs or systemic interventions or psychoeducation or psychotherapy or Intensive service models or activity based therapies).ti.
3	exp Mental Health/ or exp Mental Disorders/
4	(technolog* or digital or online or internet or mobile or electronic* or social media or smartphone* or web or app* or "VR" or "AR" or virtual reality or augmented reality or wearable or computer* or message* or personal digital assistant* or PDAS* or laptop* or e-reader* or Enterprise digital assistant* or EDA).ti.
5	2 or 3
6	(sub-Saharan Africa* or Angola* or Benin* or Botswana* or Burkina Faso* or Burundi* or Cabo Verde* or Cameroon* or Central African Republic* or Chad* or Comoros* or Congo* or Democratic Republic of Congo* or Republic of Cote d'Ivoire* or Ivory Coast* or Equatorial Guinea* or Eritrea* or Eswatini* or Ethiopia* or Gabon* or The Gambia* or Ghana* or Guinea* or Guinea-Bissau* or Kenya* or Lesotho* or Liberia* or Madagascar* or Malawi* or Mali* or Mauritania* or Mauritius* or Mozambique* or Namibia* or Niger* or Nigeria* or Rwanda* or Sao Tome* or Principe* or Senegal* or Seychelles* or Sierra Leone* or Somalia* or South Africa* or South Sudan* or Sudan* or Tanzania* or Togo* or Uganda* or Zambia* or Zimbabwe*).mp. [mp=abstract, title, original title, heading words, cabicodes words]
7	1 and 4 and 5 and 6
8	8 limit 7 to up=20130101-20240630
Total	144

PsycINFO (Ovid) Onsite Access -311	
1	(intervention* or treat* or therap* or manag* or diagnos* or counsel*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
2	(mental or psych* or anxiety or depress* or Schizophreni* or Ptsd or trauma* or panic or bipolar or paranoia or phobia or OCD or dissociati* or CBT or cognitive behavioral therapy or eye movement desensitization reprocessing or EMDR or relationship based interventions or RBIs or systemic interventions or psychoeducation or psychotherapy or Intensive service models or activity based therapies).ti.
3	exp Mental Health/ or exp Mental Disorders/
4	(technolog* or digital or online or internet or mobile or electronic* or social media or smartphone* or web or app* or "VR" or "AR" or virtual reality or augmented reality or wearable or computer* or message* or personal digital assistant* or PDAS* or laptop* or e-reader* or Enterprise digital assistant* or EDA).ti.
5	2 or 3
6	(sub-Saharan Africa* or Angola* or Benin* or Botswana* or Burkina Faso* or Burundi* or Cabo Verde* or Cameroon* or Central African Republic* or Chad* or Comoros* or Congo* or Democratic Republic of Congo* or Republic of Cote d'Ivoire* or Ivory Coast* or Equatorial Guinea* or Eritrea* or Eswatini* or Ethiopia* or Gabon* or The Gambia* or Ghana* or Guinea* or Guinea-Bissau* or Kenya* or Lesotho* or Liberia* or Madagascar* or Malawi* or Mali* or Mauritania* or Mauritius* or Mozambique* or Namibia* or Niger* or Nigeria* or Rwanda* or Sao Tome* or Principe* or Senegal* or Seychelles* or Sierra Leone* or Somalia* or South Africa* or South Sudan* or Sudan* or Tanzania* or Togo* or Uganda* or Zambia* or Zimbabwe*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]
7	1 and 4 and 5 and 6
8	limit 7 to up=20130101-20240630
Total	311

Medline (Ovid) Onsite Access -290	
1	(intervention* or treat* or therap* or manag* or diagnos* or counsel*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]
2	(mental or psych* or anxiety or depress* or Schizophreni* or Ptsd or trauma* or panic or bipolar or paranoia or phobia or OCD or dissociati* or CBT or cognitive behavioral therapy or eye movement desensitization reprocessing or EMDR or relationship-based interventions or RBIs or systemic interventions or psychoeducation or psychotherapy or Intensive service models or activity based therapies).ti.
3	exp Mental Health/ or exp Mental Disorders/
4	(technolog* or digital or online or internet or mobile or electronic* or social media or smartphone* or web or app* or "VR" or "AR" or virtual reality or augmented reality or wearable or computer* or message* or personal digital assistant* or PDAS* or laptop* or e-reader* or Enterprise digital assistant* or EDA).ti.
5	2 or 3
6	(sub-Saharan Africa* or Angola* or Benin* or Botswana* or Burkina Faso* or Burundi* or Cabo Verde* or Cameroon* or Central African Republic* or Chad* or Comoros* or Congo* or Democratic Republic of Congo* or Republic of Cote d'Ivoire* or Ivory Coast* or Equatorial Guinea* or Eritrea* or Eswatini* or Ethiopia* or Gabon* or The Gambia* or Ghana* or Guinea* or Guinea-Bissau* or Kenya* or Lesotho* or Liberia* or Madagascar* or Malawi* or Mali* or Mauritania* or Mauritius* or Mozambique* or Namibia* or Niger* or Nigeria* or Rwanda* or Sao Tome* or Principe* or Senegal* or Seychelles* or Sierra Leone* or Somalia* or South Africa* or South Sudan* or Sudan* or Tanzania* or Togo* or Uganda* or Zambia* or Zimbabwe*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]
7	1 and 4 and 5 and 6
8	limit 7 to dt=20130101-20240630
Total	290

Cochrane-83	
1	(intervention* or treat* or therap* or manag* or diagnos* or counsel*):ti,ab,kw
2	(mental or psych* or anxiety or depress* or Schizophreni* or Ptsd or trauma* or panic or bipolar or paranoia or phobia or OCD or dissociati* or CBT or cognitive behavioral therapy or eye movement desensitization reprocessing or EMDR or relationship based interventions or RBIs or systemic interventions or psychoeducation or psychotherapy or Intensive service models or activity based therapies):ti,ab,kw
3	(exp Mental Health or exp Mental Disorders):ti,ab,kw
4	(technolog* or digital or online or internet or mobile or electronic* or social media or smartphone* or web or app* or "VR" or "AR" or virtual reality or augmented reality or wearable or computer* or message* or personal digital assistant* or PDAS* or laptop* or e-reader* or Enterprise digital assistant* or EDA):ti,ab,kw
5	#2 or #3
6	(sub-Saharan Africa* or Angola* or Benin* or Botswana* or Burkina Faso* or Burundi* or Cabo Verde* or Cameroon* or Central African Republic* or Chad* or Comoros* or Congo* or Democratic Republic of Congo* or Republic of Cote d'Ivoire* or Ivory Coast* or Equatorial Guinea* or Eritrea* or Eswatini* or Ethiopia* or Gabon* or The Gambia* or Ghana* or Guinea* or Guinea-Bissau* or Kenya* or Lesotho* or Liberia* or Madagascar* or Malawi* or Mali* or Mauritania* or Mauritius* or Mozambique* or Namibia* or Niger* or Nigeria* or Rwanda* or Sao Tome* or Principe* or Senegal* or Seychelles* or Sierra Leone* or Somalia* or South Africa* or South Sudan* or Sudan* or Tanzania* or Togo* or Uganda* or Zambia* or Zimbabwe*):ti,ab,kw
7	#7 #1 and #4 and #5 and #6 with Cochrane Library publication date from Jan 2013 to Jun 2024
Total	83

WHO Publication Library-9 (Searched on 01/07/2024)	
1	"Digital Health Interventions"
Total	9

UN iLibrary-1 (Searched on 01/07/2024)	
1	"Digital Health Interventions"
Total	1

APPENDIX 2: MMAT VERSION 2018

Part I: Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT), version 2018

Category of study designs	Methodological quality criteria	Responses			
		Yes	No	Can't tell	Comments
Screening questions (for all types)	S1. Are there clear research questions?				
	S2. Do the collected data allow to address the research questions?				
	<i>Further appraisal may not be feasible or appropriate when the answer is 'No' or 'Can't tell' to one or both screening questions.</i>				
1. Qualitative	1.1. Is the qualitative approach appropriate to answer the research question?				
	1.2. Are the qualitative data collection methods adequate to address the research question?				
	1.3. Are the findings adequately derived from the data?				
	1.4. Is the interpretation of results sufficiently substantiated by data?				
	1.5. Is there coherence between qualitative data sources, collection, analysis and interpretation?				
2. Quantitative randomized controlled trials	2.1. Is randomization appropriately performed?				
	2.2. Are the groups comparable at baseline?				
	2.3. Are there complete outcome data?				
	2.4. Are outcome assessors blinded to the intervention provided?				
	2.5. Did the participants adhere to the assigned intervention?				
3. Quantitative non-randomized	3.1. Are the participants representative of the target population?				
	3.2. Are measurements appropriate regarding both the outcome and intervention (or exposure)?				
	3.3. Are there complete outcome data?				
	3.4. Are the confounders accounted for in the design and analysis?				
	3.5. During the study period, is the intervention administered (or exposure occurred) as intended?				
4. Quantitative descriptive	4.1. Is the sampling strategy relevant to address the research question?				
	4.2. Is the sample representative of the target population?				
	4.3. Are the measurements appropriate?				
	4.4. Is the risk of nonresponse bias low?				
	4.5. Is the statistical analysis appropriate to answer the research question?				
5. Mixed methods	5.1. Is there an adequate rationale for using a mixed methods design to address the research question?				
	5.2. Are the different components of the study effectively integrated to answer the research question?				
	5.3. Are the outputs of the integration of qualitative and quantitative components adequately interpreted?				
	5.4. Are divergences and inconsistencies between quantitative and qualitative results adequately addressed?				
	5.5. Do the different components of the study adhere to the quality criteria of each tradition of the methods involved?				

APPENDIX 3: THE MIXED METHODS APPRAISAL RESULTS

Critical Appraisal Results (MMAT)

Study Reference	S1	S2	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	2.1	2.2	2.3 (>80%)	2.4	2.5	3.1	3.2	3.3 (>80%)	3.4	3.5	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4	4.5	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	MMAT Rating (% Criteria Met)
81	Yes	Yes	1	1	1	1	1											1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	80%
82	Yes	Yes	1	1	1	1	1																					100%
83	Yes	Yes	1	1	1	1	1																					100%
84	Yes	Yes	1	1	1	0	1						1	1	0	1	0						1	1	1	1	1	60%
85	Yes	Yes	1	0	1	1	1																1	1	1	1	1	80%
86	Yes	Yes	1	1	1	1	1											1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	60%
87	Yes	Yes																0	0	1	1	1						60%
88	Yes	Yes						1	1	0	1	0																60%
89	Yes	Yes	1	1	1	1	1						0	1	1	1	1						1	1	1	1	1	80%
90	Yes	Yes						1	1	0	1	0																60%
91	Yes	Yes											0	1	1	1	1											80%
92	Yes	Yes						1	1	0	1	0																60%
93	Yes	Yes						1	1	0	1	0																60%
94	Yes	Yes											1	1	0	0	1											60%
95	Yes	Yes						1	1	0	1	0																60%
96	Yes	Yes						1	1	1	1	1																100%
97	Yes	Yes						0	1	1	0	1																60%
98	Yes	Yes											1	1	0	1	1											80%
99	Yes	Yes						1	1	0	1	0																60%
100	Yes	Yes						1	1	1	0	0																60%

APPENDIX 4: TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Study Ref	Location	Intervention Settings	Study Aim (s)	Study Methods and Designs	Participants (N=Number)	Study Findings	Study Limitations	The Healthcare Access Framework Dimensions	MMAT Rating (%)
81	Kenya	Four public health facilities in Kibwezi district, Makueni county, and digitally	To investigate the use of a mobile based mental health mhGAP-IG to determine the prevalence and determinants of depression in remote healthcare settings and evaluate the feasibility of the application.	Mixed methods study Socio-demographic questionnaire was utilised alongside a focus group discussion (FGDs).	(N= 1664) respondents with a mean age of 41.	25% of the patients who were assessed were found to have depression, and suicidal conduct was the most associated issue. The participants deemed the application to be viable for identifying depression	The reliability of mhGAP-IG has yet to be resolved, with its only source of credibility being the endorsement by the WHO.	Supply Availability and accommodation Appropriateness Demand Ability to reach Ability to engage	80
82	South Africa	Stellenbosch University and digitally	To examine the experiences of South African university students who have utilised a ICBT for depression and document the level of acceptability of this form of psychotherapy.	Qualitative study The data was gathered through an online mental health screening survey, which encompassed a sociodemographic questionnaire. Furthermore, comprehensive semi-structured interviews were conducted with students who had completed all 7 sessions of the ICBT.	(N= 9) participants with a mean age of 18.9.	At the one-month follow-up, 80% of the individuals who finished the program experienced notable decreases of their depression symptoms, which were considered clinically significant. Participants reported that their experience of using the e-intervention was predominantly appealing, readily accessible, and effectively supported relief from symptoms.	A small sample size and the restriction of participants to first-year students exclusively from a single university.	Supply Approachability Acceptability Availability and accommodation Appropriateness Demand Ability to perceive Ability to seek Ability to reach Ability to engage	100
83	South Africa	University in South Africa and digitally	To investigate university students' experiences of a GCBT intervention for the treatment of symptoms of depression and anxiety.	Qualitative study Single open-ended online questionnaire item was sent, and in-depth interviews with randomly selected participants.	(N= 158) participants. 125 participants completed the qualitative questionnaire, and 12 participated in the in-depth interviews.	The findings showed that GCBT improved the mental health state of participants.	A limited number of selected participants successfully finished the interviews, suggesting certain level of selection bias. Furthermore, the university's student population does not accurately reflect the wider demographics of the country's university populace.	Supply Acceptability Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to engage	100
84	Zimbabwe	Digitally	To assess the feasibility of carrying out a prospective clinical study and the feasibility, acceptability, appropriateness, scalability, and initial effectiveness of Inuka.	Mixed methods study A pragmatic non-equivalent control group quasi experimental design was employed, where the Inuka intervention served as the experimental group and the WhatsApp intervention served as the control group. Data implementation aspects were investigated using semi-structured interviews.	(N= 176) participants with a mean age of 24.4.	Inuka was deemed feasible and acceptable in the local context. Generally, there was a decline in depression and anxiety in both groups.	Conveniently assignment of participants to intervention groups may have introduced selection bias. Secondly, there was a considerable loss to follow-up in the Inuka intervention arm.	Supply Acceptability Availability and accommodation Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to reach Ability to engage	60

85	Zambia	Digitally	To investigate adolescents' and young adults' experiences when shifting to remotely delivered services during the COVID-19 pandemic.	Qualitative study Participants were randomly selected to participate in qualitative interviews.	(N= 16) participants between the ages of 15-29 years.	Participants reported that the telehealth delivery intervention improved mental disorders such as anxiety and PTSD stress and reduced some access barriers to engaging in mental health care provision in Zambia.	Responses elicited during these qualitative interviews are susceptible to social desirability bias due to the study design and Zambian context.	Supply Acceptability Availability and accommodation Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to reach Ability to engage	80
86	Zambia	Digitally	To examine and ascertain the viewpoints of both clients and therapists regarding the efficacy of online counselling during the pandemic, focussing on the level of readiness, method of implementation, and encountered difficulties.	Mixed methods study Data were collected in two phases: questionnaire and use of FGDs.	(N= 284) participants with (N= 44) therapists and (N= 240) counselling clients.	Researchers found that online counselling was ineffective for patients experiencing mental disorders during the COVID-19 pandemic.	There was no consideration given to defining the indicators for effectiveness to the participants, which could have led to different interpretations of what effectiveness means.	Supply Approachability Availability and accommodation Affordability Appropriateness Demand Ability to perceive Ability to reach Ability to pay Ability to engage	60
87	South Africa	Digitally with the website (MDDS.co.za)	To evaluate the efficacy of the online adapted Centre for Epidemiology Studies Depression Scale-Revised (CESD-R) for use in South Africa by reporting on the reliability, instant feedback of the website.	Quantitative study Data was collected through a survey consisting of a brief demographic questionnaire.	(N= 107) participants above the age of 18.	The online adapted CESD-R demonstrated excellent reliability and criterion validity, and it was able to accurately screen for depression among South Africans.	The sample size of the study was small, and the COVID-19 pandemic may have caused many participants to experience depressive symptoms.	Supply Appropriateness Demand Ability to engage	60
88	Nigeria	10 primary care centres in Lagos, Nigeria, and digitally	To assess the efficacy and acceptability of including mobile phone adherence support into a collaborative stepped care (CSC) intervention for the primary care treatment of depression.	Quantitative study Participants were randomised into either the mobile telephone supported CSC (mCSC) group or the ordinary CSC (oCSC) group in ratio 1:1.	(N= 895) participants. The mCSC group (N= 439 participants) and CSC group (N= 456 participants).	The mCSC group demonstrated a markedly superior adherence rate in comparison to the oCSC group at various stages of follow-up. The mCSC had an improved recovery rate from depression, enhanced quality of life, greater rate of retention in therapy, and a notable level of acceptance among users.	Self-rating scales were not used for the adherence scores, which may not fully capture participants' perspectives on the impact of the intervention on adherence.	Supply Acceptability Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to engage	60
89	Kenya	Digitally	To explore the acceptability and feasibility of a mobile based counselling and peer support intervention for adolescents living with HIV (ALWH) in western Kenya.	Mixed methods study Participants' adherence to HIV treatment, experiences with stigma, mental and behavioural health, and clinical status were assessed at different periods. In addition, pre- and post-intervention interviews were carried out.	(N= 25) and (N= 15) participants for pre- and post-intervention interviews respectively with a mean age of 15.4.	The study showed that WhatsApp platform was an acceptable and feasible strategy for delivering mobile counselling for improving mental health and providing mental health and peer support for ALWH.	The follow-up only lasted six months, and the sample size was small.	Supply Acceptability Availability and accommodation Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to reach Ability to engage	80

90	South Africa	Psychiatric hospital in Cape Town and digitally	To investigate intervention acceptability and feasibility for patients diagnosed with schizophrenia spectrum disorder, substance induced psychotic disorder, and bipolar mood disorder type I.	Quantitative study Participants were randomised to either intervention or treatment as usual. Interviews were also conducted with participants, caregivers, and treatment partners.	(N= 77) participants with (N= 42) randomised to receive the intervention and (N= 35) to treatment as usual.	The treatment partner and psychoeducation components were deemed acceptable and practicable. The text message component was deemed satisfactory but impractical in its present state. The intervention showed favourable efficacy outcomes, albeit they did not achieve statistical significance.	For the efficacy analyses, the sample size lacked sufficient power. Mental health nurses experienced challenges interacting with the text message system that compromised appointment checking and rescheduling.	Supply Acceptability Availability and accommodation Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to reach Ability to engage	60
91	Ghana	Prayer camp and digitally	To examine the feasibility, acceptability, safety, and preliminary effectiveness of the M&M intervention (8-weeklong dual-prolonged intervention of the M-Healer app and mhGAP-IG version 2.0) in real world prayer camp settings.	Quantitative study Data was collected through study assessors, self-reporting assessments, and interviews with patient participants. Additionally, study assessors reports and self-reports from healers were also utilised.	(N=17) participants.	The M&M intervention proved to be feasible, acceptable, safe, and clinically promising for symptoms of schizophrenia and bipolar.	The use of a single prayer camp limits study generality. Secondly, the use of self-reports may have led to reporting bias. Thirdly, the study sample was small, allowing only for preliminary examination of treatment effects.	Supply Acceptability Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to engage	80
92	South Africa	Two non-governmental organisations and two public sector primary care clinics in Cape Town and digitally	To assess the impact of automated text messages to women undergoing medical abortion on anxiety and emotional distress associated with abortion.	Quantitative study Data was collected through interviews with participants and evaluations of different anxiety and depression scales.	(N = 469) participants randomly allocated to two groups. The intervention group consisted of (N = 234) participants, while the control group consisted of (N = 235).	Interacting via text with women after they have taken mifepristone for an early medical abortion can help them handle symptoms and is well-received by the recipients.	There was bias towards better-resourced population than the national average.	Supply Acceptability Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to engage	60
93	Kenya	Private clinics in Nairobi County and digitally	To assess the impact of a mobile-based intervention focused on person-centred abortion care on the perception of social stigma, social support, mental health, and post-abortion care experiences among women in Kenya.	Quantitative study Participants were randomised into three study arms. Kruskal-Wallis's test was used to assess the effect of each intervention group compared to the control group.	(N= 371) female participants at baseline. (N=122) participants randomised to control, (N= 122) to peer counsellor, and (N= 127) to nurse.	The use of person-centred mobile phone-based intervention may improve mental health and decrease perceived stigma among Kenyan women who received abortion services in private clinics.	The intervention included only one peer counsellor and one nurse. Secondly, there was bias in participant selection, which may not be generalizable. Finally, disruptions in the study due to Kenya's legally restrictive context.	Supply Appropriateness Demand Ability to engage	60
94	South Africa	Learning environment and digitally	To evaluate the efficacy of brain-computer interface (BCI) mathematics educational game in training and reducing math anxiety.	Quantitative study Data was collected from the same sample at different points in time to determine how the participants managed and controlled their anxiety levels with the BCI neurofeedback.	(N= 36) participants with a mean age of 14.06.	The evaluation of data collected from two training sessions using a BCI mathematics instructional game revealed that math anxiety can be successfully addressed and diminished through BCI training.	The components of the application that significantly contribute to the reduction in the level of math anxiety were not captured. In addition, the use of one single emotional component limits determining the role that other emotional components could play in the training and reducing math anxiety.	Supply Appropriateness Demand Ability to engage	60
95	Nigeria	Psychiatric Clinic in Benin and digitally	To investigate the impact of sending short messaging service (SMS) reminders to patients with first-episode	Quantitative study The impact of the intervention was assessed by using per-protocol analysis after	(N= 192) with a mean age of 33.7.	Sending SMS reminders for appointments is a successful intervention to enhance clinic attendance among individuals	The delivery of the SMS messages was not verified.	Supply Appropriateness Demand	60

			psychosis who are seeking treatment for the first time, on their likelihood of attending their next planned clinic visit.	randomisation of patients into two control and intervention groups.		receiving treatment for first-episode psychosis at the Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital in Benin City, Nigeria.		Ability to engage	
96	Kenya	Mixed secondary school in Kiambu County and digitally	To determine the efficacy of a brief, computerised single-session intervention (Shamiri-Digital) in reducing symptoms of depression and anxiety.	Quantitative study Data was collected from completed participants' assessments at baseline and 2-week follow-up of control and intervention groups.	(N=103) participants between the ages of 13 and 18.	Shamiri-Digital produced a greater reduction in adolescent depressive symptoms. There were no significant effects on anxiety symptoms, well-being, or happiness.	The sample size was not large enough to detect small to medium differences between conditions. Secondly, a short follow-up period was observed.	Supply Acceptability Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to engage	100
97	Rwanda	Kigali, Rwamagana, and Huye localities and digitally	To assess the efficacy of neurofeedback (NF) and motor imagery (MI) brain-computer interface (BCI) training, utilising affordable electroencephalography-based wearable neurotechnology in a non-clinical environment, as a viable therapy for PTSD in Rwanda.	Quantitative study Data was analysed by the pre- and post-intervention clinical assessments of the three different groups. The three groups were Control (no training), NF (7 sessions), and MI (6 sessions).	(N= 29) participants. The participants number were split into control (N= 9), NF (N = 10), and MI, (N= 10).	The results showed a clinically relevant reduction in PTSD symptom severity in the NF group.	The sample size was small, and data collection took place in environments that posed difficulties in controlling environmental factors.	Supply Appropriateness Demand Ability to engage	60
98	Kenya	Primary care services in Ruiru County and digitally	To assess the efficacy of a PST intervention administered by community health volunteers via a mobile application named 'Inuka coaching' in Kenya.	Quantitative study Data was collected and analysed through different self-reporting questionnaires on different mental health reporting tools.	(N= 80) participants consented to the study, of which 60 participants (female, N = 38; male, N= 22) completed their 4-week assessments, and 52 participants completed their 3-month follow-up assessment.	The results showed a significant improvement in mental health over time with the use of intervention.	The use of a single-arm, naturalistic follow-up study in which no control condition was used. Secondly, the use of only participants who can speak and write English makes generalization difficult due to Kenya's multi-language setting.	Supply Acceptability Appropriateness Demand Ability to seek Ability to engage	80
99	Nigeria	The University of Nigeria, Nsukka and digitally	To assess the effectiveness of GIAL in reducing depression among educational technology students at Nigerian universities.	Quantitative study Self-reporting questionnaire was used for data collection. Data was analysed using the analysis of variance with repeated measures.	(N=192) participants. (N=96) participants were randomly allocated into two groups: the treatment group and the usual-care control group.	The findings demonstrated that after 10 weeks of involvement in GIAL, the evaluation outcomes indicated a noteworthy decrease in depression among students in the intervention group in comparison to those in the control group receiving standard therapy.	The sample size included only educational students in a particular Nigerian university. Secondly, the efficacy of GIAL was assessed using an instrument that produced essentially quantitative data. In addition, there were no demographic variables in the analysis.	Supply Appropriateness Demand Ability to engage	60
100	South Africa	Three university campuses and digitally	To assess the efficacy of remote group CBT skills training and the SuperBetter training software compared to an active control group (MoodFlow) in a population of anxious and/or depressed university students in South Africa.	Quantitative study Data was collected through self-reported assessment questionnaires. Analysis of data was done with score modelling and outcome modelling.	(N=371) participants. The participants were randomised with equal allocation to remote group CBT skills training, SuperBetter, or a MoodFlow mood monitoring control.	The findings indicate that SuperBetter application and the remote group CBT skills training intervention were more effective than a mood monitoring control condition in treating depression and anxiety in university students, as shown during follow-up periods.	The sample size was low, and the use of self-reported measures instead of clinical assessment may have reduced the quality of results. Additionally, there was no assessment of either intervention acceptability.	Supply Appropriateness Demand Ability to engage	60

APPENDIX 5: EXISTING DMHI IDENTIFIED FROM THIS STUDY AND UTILISATION IN MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES ACROSS SSA

Ref	Existing DMHI in SSA Identified from this Study	Country	Utilisation in Mental Health Services
81	Mobile based mhGAP-IG	Kenya	Screening, prevalence and determinants of depression in remote settings.
82	ICBT	South Africa	Improve symptoms depression in university students.
83	Online GCBT	South Africa	Improve symptoms of anxiety and depression.
84	Inuka- mobile application hinged on the Friendship Bench PST	Zimbabwe	Improve symptoms of anxiety and depression.
85	Telephone delivery of the Common Elements Treatment Approach	Zambia	Improve symptoms of anxiety and PTSD.
86	Online counselling through video conferencing, phone calls and text messages	Zambia	Used to improve symptoms of anxiety, depression and stress but was ineffective.
87	Electronic version of the CESD-R	South Africa	Online screening of depression.
88	Mobile telephone adherence support to a CSC intervention	Nigeria	Enhance management of depression in primary care.
89	WhatsApp platform to deliver mobile counselling and peer support	Kenya	Improve overall mental health state.
90	Text message system to deliver psychoeducation and reminders for clinic appointments	South Africa	Provide psychological education and clinic appointment reminders for individuals with bipolar mood disorder type I, substance-induced psychotic disorder, and schizophrenia diagnosis.
91	M&M intervention-8 weeklong dual combination of a M-Healer mobile application and mobile version of the WHO's mhGAP-IG version 2.0	Ghana	Improve symptoms of schizophrenia and bipolar.
92	Text messages to deliver messages as part of abortion care	South Africa	Alleviate anxiety and emotional distress associated with medical abortion.
93	SMS, text messages and phone calls to provide stigma, social, mental health and post-abortion care support	Kenya	Improve overall mental health state after abortion.
94	Maths Mind-a BCI mathematics educational game	South Africa	Reduce anxiety associated with mathematics in students.

95	SMS reminders for psychosis appointments	Nigeria	Increase patient adherence and engagement with mental health care in clinical settings.
96	Shamiri-Digital- brief, computerised single-session interventions that contain empirically supported stigma-reducing elements	Kenya	Improve symptoms of depression.
97	An NF and MI based BCI training using low-cost electroencephalography wearable neurotechnology	Rwanda	For treating symptoms of PTSD.
98	Inuka coaching -mobile application to deliver PST.	Kenya	Improve symptoms of anxiety and depression.
99	GIAI- a 10-week of psychoeducation, interactive peer support, cognitive disputation, behavioural homework assignments, role-play and depression management	Nigeria	Improve symptoms of depression in university students.
100	Remote GCBT skills training- 10-week skills training delivered online via video conferencing platform by trained psychologists	South Africa	Improve symptoms in university students with clinically significant anxiety and depression.
100	SuperBetter- CBT skills training mobile application	South Africa	Improve symptoms in university students with clinically significant anxiety and depression.
100	MoodFlow- mood tracking mobile application	South Africa	Improve symptoms in university students with clinically significant anxiety and depression.

